

The Role of DDI-CDI in EOSC: Possible Uses and Applications

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Please cite this document as: Gregory, A., Hodson, S., Wackerow, J., 2021, 'The Role of DDI-CDI in EOSC: Possible Uses and Applications', <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4707263>

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the EOSC Secretariat.

[EOSCsecretariat.eu](https://eosccsecretariat.eu) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-4, Grant Agreement number 831644.

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Summary

This report looks at the potential use of the Data Documentation Initiative Cross-Domain Integration (DDI-CDI) specification to the data-sharing requirements faced by EOSC. By analyzing real-world projects and implementations, and through discussion with those responsible for related metadata and infrastructure specifications, the potential role played by the DDI-CDI model in the overall EOSC system is envisioned, and recommendations made for how to realize the identified opportunities for its use.

The challenges faced by EOSC can be broken into two main areas:

- **Problems of Scale:** The volume of data is growing exponentially and is coming from a wider range of sources. At the same time, the FAIR principles require an increased amount of metadata, especially when it comes to interoperability and reuse of that data. Current manual approaches are proving to be unsustainable. The automation of metadata collection - that is, harvesting metadata programmatically from systems which produce, manage, disseminate, and use data - offers a possible solution, but the necessary framework for such activities is not in place. Standard models and encoding for such metadata (a "lingua franca") must be established for large-scale capture and exchange of metadata.

- **Problems of Cross-Domain Use:** In order for data to be shared across domain and institutional boundaries, it must be understood by its users at all levels. While increasing attention is paid to the semantic mapping of concepts across domains, there are other critical needs for such data sharing. Disparate data structures must be accommodated, based on the tools and formats used in specific domains, and the means of data collection and processing - the provenance of the data - must be understood. Use of specific domain models and vocabularies must be known, and they must be accessible in a machine-actionable form. Reusable crosswalks between domains are needed. All of these requirements point to the need for more granular metadata, so that data can be successfully re-arranged to be suitable for use outside its domain of origin. The path of a single observation, as it is reused and further processed, should be knowable.

DDI-CDI will not address all of these concerns; no single standard or technology will provide a complete answer. It has, however, been designed to fill important gaps in the needed range of standards, models, and technologies to meet these challenges. On the basis of an intensive series of meetings, conference sessions, workshops and other discussions with a range of different groups, this report looks at use cases and the emerging FAIR ecosystem to understand the potential application of DDI-CDI, and the role it could play within a broader frame. The approach being taken by EOSC—as described in the EOSC Interoperability Framework and in other activities—is then assessed to show specifically where DDI-CDI would fit. Recommendations for further work are then made on that basis.

Specific implementation examples include a data integration using climate data, energy consumption data, and consumer questionnaire responses; an example of how a repository could facilitate automated capture of metadata, based on the Dataverse platform; a data integration example from the European Social Survey Multi-Level application; and an exploration of processing, provenance, and cross-domain requirements as seen in the ALPHA Network and INSPIRE applications for the integration of population and clinical data. An analysis of how DDI-CDI could be used in combination with DCAT is presented, and the role which DDI-CDI could play within the emerging FAIR ecosystem, in relation to FAIR Implementation Profiles, FAIR Data Points, and FAIR Digital Objects, is examined. Finally, the way in which DDI-CDI could be integrated into the emerging

EOSC infrastructure is considered in light of the EOSC Interoperability Framework and the FAIRsFAIR vision of integrated metadata catalogues.

DDI-CDI offers a new type of specification which could help to realize the capture, interchange, and use of metadata throughout the EOSC data-sharing infrastructure, and could do so in ways which are scalable and machine-actionable. It operates at the needed level of granularity and would work to heighten the utility of semantic mapping and approaches to the full utilization of data. Our recommendations identify several concrete areas where this application of the model should be further explored.

I. Background: DDI-CDI and the Suite of DDI Work Products

A. Overview

DDI-CDI is a metadata standard designed to facilitate the exchange and reuse of data across domain boundaries, acting as a supplemental resource to other domain vocabularies and standards for metadata. Developed by the DDI Alliance, a body which has for decades produced detailed metadata standards for the social, behavioural, and economic (SBE) sciences—supplemented by a strong degree of interest and use from the public health and official statistical domains—DDI-CDI represents a departure, but one which reflects demands coming from the increasingly interdisciplinary nature of modern research.

Among other things, DDI-CDI is designed to characterise data structure, thus allowing and facilitating automation of the processes needed to combine data. As such, it is a domain agnostic specification and can interact with a range of metadata standards. Nevertheless, in relation to the motivations for its development and to understand some of the implementation examples given later in this report, it is useful to understand how DDI-CDI builds on earlier DDI standards.

For a list of the activities contributing to this report, please see “The Role of DDI-CDI in EOSC: Report on Activities”.

B. DDI-Codebook (DDI 1 and DDI 2)

Since the release in 2001 of the first DDI metadata specification, DDI has become a common tool for data archives and repositories in the SBE sciences, both in Europe and across the globe. The DDI-Codebook specification is the version which is most used. It is a platform-neutral, machine-readable specification for describing data sets.

The scope of a single DDI-Codebook description is the “study”: one wave of data, collected at a single point in time in support of a research project, which produces a single data file or a collection of related data files (e.g., a persons file and a households file). The primary requirement was for describing data resulting from survey data collection, although other forms of data (i.e., register data) can also be described. Tabulations of the study data for the purposes of describing the tables which support research findings are also supported.

DDI-Codebook has been used by two major initiatives which have resulted in its widespread use (200+ countries across the world, notably in Africa and Asia). The International Household Survey Network—a collaboration among several UN organizations focused on low and middle-income countries (LMIC) statistical agencies and the dissemination of their data—produces and distributes a range of tools and capacity building materials based on DDI-Codebook. These include the ability to create documentation files for surveys, and to provide online dissemination sites and catalogues.

Perhaps more important from our perspective, DDI-Codebook was also adopted as a standard by CESSDA (the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives, now a European Research Infrastructure Consortium [ERIC]). Through the line of Nesstar tools, the data archives were able to document and expose their holdings and to provide a Europe-wide multi-lingual catalogue. Nesstar and DDI-Codebook also provided a basis for many collaborations between the European archives.

Nesstar and DDI-Codebook have also been adopted in many other countries, notably within Canada and in many US institutions, including for describing the IPUMS International harmonized census data.

DDI-Codebook is the simplest of the major DDI metadata specifications, relying on a mature technology (XML), a proven tool base, and a broad community of use. It is, however, limited in that it only describes data for a single wave of collection at one point in time, and cannot describe the relationships between disparate data sets. Further, it does not support data production scenarios or metadata reuse. It is limited in its data description to primarily unit-record (“rectangular”) data files, which are the typical way in which microdata is formatted in the SBE sciences.

C. DDI-Lifecycle (DDI 3)

DDI-Lifecycle came out of the demand within the DDI community for a metadata standard which supported not only after-the-fact description of data files, but one which would describe the data production lifecycle, and allow for the accumulation of metadata as data was being produced. Further, there was a need to describe longitudinal and other repeated data collection, and to compare similar data from different sources. Inherent in this picture is the idea of metadata reuse.

The specification was first published in 2009. Although it has not been as widely adopted as DDI-Codebook, this is not unexpected: while providing a much broader range of functionality, it is commensurately more complex. Data producers—statistical agencies and on-going longitudinal surveys—have adopted it, as it serves their primary function as producers of data for whom comparison of data across time is significant.

DDI-Lifecycle also provided a higher degree of support for machine-actionability, including in the description of questionnaires. This results in the ability to use the specification for “metadata-driven” applications where efficiencies can be gained by leveraging metadata as it accumulates throughout the production life cycle, and indeed between cycles of collection for the same or similar data.

DDI-Lifecycle provides the ability to describe not just a single data set, but a group of them, coming from disparate sources. The similarities and differences can be documented, and the shared metadata can be stored once and used many times by reference. The type of metadata reuse which DDI-Lifecycle supports makes it well-suited for metadata management and dissemination (e.g., classification management, question banks, etc.), and for documenting the integration of data sets.

Like DDI-Codebook, it relies on XML as its primary technology implementation. As a result of demand from the user community, DDI also produced a set of RDF Vocabularies for data discovery and for statistical classifications which were based on the existing DDI specifications, in recognition that RDF technologies were becoming more prevalent in the SBE sciences.

Also like DDI-Codebook, the type of data described is primarily unit-record data (“rectangular”) although the ability to describe some types of non-survey data was also expanded. DDI-Lifecycle is well-supported by both open-source and commercial tools offerings.

D. DDI Controlled Vocabularies

Controlled vocabularies play a critical role in metadata standards. A set of controlled vocabularies is developed by the DDI Alliance to be used to describe specific aspects of a dataset in DDI specifications and for other use. The controlled vocabularies cover SBE and cross-domain subjects. They support interoperability and machine-actionability. Most of these controlled vocabularies are integrated in the CESSDA Vocabulary Service¹.

E. The DDI 4 “Moving Forward” Project

Following the release of the DDI-Lifecycle specification, a further expansion of scope was anticipated, to cover additional parts of the data lifecycle (e.g., methodology and experimental design, data management planning, etc.), to generalize the scope beyond the SBE domain as well as alignment with some emerging standards, notably the Generic Statistical Information Model (GSIM) and provenance standards such as PROV-O. Additionally, there was a decision within the community to move away from XML as the primary technology platform, and to adopt a “model-driven” approach, which could be represented in XML, RDF, or any of the other syntaxes and technology platforms which were beginning to proliferate.

What resulted was a 7-year effort (the DDI 4 “Moving Forward” project) which incorporated many of the best-of-breed models for different types of metadata from a number of different sources, and the development of a very broad model which was not designed with a single purpose in mind, but with the idea that it could function as a library from which specific implementations could be rendered. XML and RDF syntax representations were produced as part of a prototype, but the entire model has never been released as a specification, in part because of its large size and the need for specific implementations (in more focused specifications) to make it truly useful. Currently there are no plans for releasing the entire model as a single specification.

To this end, this work has had and retains a strong influence on revisions to the DDI-Lifecycle specification and is also the basis for subsequent work around DDI-CDI. The idea is that the DDI “Moving Forward” model becomes one of the bases of alignment for future work products of the Alliance.

F. DDI-CDI

1. Background

DDI-CDI was envisioned as the first separate DDI specification to be based on the DDI “Moving Forward” model, with a commitment to producing a limited-but-useful specification driven by the needs of implementers. To this end, it was built around a set of external projects being conducted by Alliance members and participants, which could test and feedback input into the model as it evolved.

It had become apparent that what was needed was not a metadata specification for SBE data, but instead an extended set of information which would support the incorporation and reuse of data in atypical forms (from an SBE perspective) and coming from sources which were often external to the DDI community. Requirements to integrate sensor data, event data, and key-value “big” data were prominent, as was the need to provide a more complete description of data provenance. More familiar was the need to integrate aggregate reference data into studies which also collected their own unit-record data.

¹ CESSDA Vocabulary Service - <https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu>

Unsurprisingly, the ability to describe a range of data sources from external domains for use within the SBE sciences is identical to the ability needed by external domains to describe each others' data. The same applies to provenance. DDI-CDI represents an attempt to generically describe data in a way that is not limited to any specific domain, or the culture of data use within it.

This is an ambitious goal, and one which is not completely supported by the current specification. The intent is clear, however: as it develops, DDI-CDI is intended to provide a supplemental set of metadata which will facilitate cross-domain data integration and reuse. It does not replace domain standards, but rather is intended to build on them to support additional functionality and new features.

It should be noted that much of the existing work on “semantic” domain models is focused on the definitional aspects of research, and how data is collected, used and analysed. This is distinct from the structural description of that data. DDI-CDI focuses on the structural, rather than the “semantic” information. Because of this, it can act as a complement to existing domain ontologies, rather than as a replacement for them. This aspect of the design is intentional.

To this end, the DDI-CDI specification is offered primarily as a formal UML model which can be implemented on any number of different technology platforms, although both XML and RDF are seen as likely candidates for such implementation. Other technologies such as JSON and Python are also expected to be significant. The model-driven aspect of the specification is seen as a means of future-proofing the work against the proliferation of technologies, both within and across domains. For the UML model, a subset of the UML class diagram notation is used which enables wide interoperability and easy mapping to any target programming language. The representation in the target languages can be generated on the basis of the DDI-CDI model.

The first production release of the DDI-CDI model is anticipated in the first half of 2021 (it was released for public review in April 2020), but requirements coming from this and other EOSC activities will be accepted by the development team as they revise the specification. A fairly rapid revision of the specification is anticipated after the production release, to incorporate lessons learned from the initial implementations. Given the newness of the area addressed—metadata specifications have not attempted to address data integration across domain boundaries in this way before—such a prompt revision cycle makes sense.

2. Supported Functionality

The main features of DDI-CDI are described below, and specific details are discussed further in relation to the particular implementation examples given in this report. Distinctively, the focus of DDI-CDI is on the aspects of data and process description which are domain-independent, and it assumes the use of additional vocabularies and metadata standards which can provide domain-specific information.

More detail on DDI-CDI² can be found on the DDI Alliance website, including draft specifications and comments, recordings of webinars, and more.

Foundational Metadata

In order to describe data, especially across the range of types encountered in cross-domain data use, a large number of basic “building blocks” need to be established. DDI-CDI has a very rich model for these foundational metadata, incorporating many prior models coming from other DDI

² DDI-CDI - <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/ddi-cdi>

specifications and elsewhere, notably from the Generic Statistical Information Model (GSIM)³. Some important elements are described here, although this list is in no way exhaustive.

Concepts are an important part of the formal description of data and serve as a bridge between many different metadata structures as they connect to data. The formal definition of concepts and the different ways they relate to data and descriptive metadata are provided by the DDI-CDI specification in a thorough fashion.

Classifications and *code lists* are another significant aspect of the DDI-CDI model, including their relationships to conceptual domains.

Variables are perhaps the most sophisticated part of the DDI-CDI model. The “variable cascade” recognizes the degrees of specificity which can be applied to variables as they evolve from their purely conceptual state to being the descriptors of specific data points. This is a levelled model capable of expressing the similarities and differences between how variables are used across data sets.

Data Points (“*datums*”, i.e. a cell of a spreadsheet) are a significant focus in the DDI-CDI model. Described as “datum-centric,” the model does not assume that a data point is defined by its location within a specific data set but recognizes that it can have a place within many different data sets and play a different structural role in each. Management of data at the level of the datum is critical in being able to understand how data is harmonized, integrated, reused, and processed.

Description of Data Structure Types

DDI-CDI uses an approach to data description which involves using a set of component constructs to assign roles (like measure and identifier) to variables and data points for each of the structural forms they take (or might potentially take). This approach is independent of the semantic roles they play but acts as a framework within which the semantics of different concepts associated with specific data points can be more completely understood. (Concepts can take their definitions from whatever vocabularies are selected – DDI-CDI does not provide any domain semantics but relies on external definitions.).

The mentioned set of component constructs (the “component toolkit”) provide, on one hand, a set of building blocks to create data structures types (like the ones described below) in the model. On the other hand, they ensure that metadata represented in one data structure type can be easily transformed to any others which have been similarly described. It is anticipated that additional data structure types are created by these means in future.

Four important types of data structure are described in the specification, along with some important sub-types. These are:

1. *Wide Data* (an alternative term is “un-stacked”) – The traditional (to the SBE) rectangular data set, in which each row is a record describing a unit, identified within the record. Each column is a single variable, applied consistently to each record. This is a common data structure in many domains, and is well-handled in analysis packages such as SAS, SPSS, R, Stata, etc.
2. *Long Data* (alternative terms are “narrow”, “stacked”, “tall”) – This is the form most often used to record streams of data coming from sensors or other continuous sources. Each

³ GSIM - <https://statswiki.unece.org/display/gsim>

observation becomes a record which indicates its unit, the observation, and a cluster of descriptive fields which contextualize the measurement. Different types of measurements are typically contained within the flow or table of data. This is a common format also for event-based data sets and administrative registers.

3. *Multi-Dimensional Data (alternate terms include “aggregate data” and “data cubes”)* - This is a use of metadata to assign variables to vectors which can produce compound identifiers for a set of observations in a notional “cube” structure. Such a data structure allows for an understanding of how observations/measures relate to each other, based on the degree of similarity between the various fields which make up their identifiers (i.e., a number measuring the percentage of a population which has a college education can be identified with an observation date, a geographic region, a sex, and an occupation code. This would allow the percentages of college-educated men and women in a given occupation to be compared for a given region and time period by simply toggling the value of the sex variable in their identifiers. Each identifier would point to a measure with a known relationship.) Indicators are a common expression of single multidimensional data points tracked across time (“time series”).
4. *Key-Value Data (alternate terms are “no SQL” data or “big” data)* - These structures are often used to describe pools of observations (“data lakes”) which can be used as the source of analysis data sets, assembled through queries, or be directly analyzed with algorithms (a common AI approach). This style of data is very common in many data integration/virtualization platforms and is often used as way of storing data coming from less-structured sources such as social media harvesting.

The public review period has identified some additional types of data structure which DDI-CDI will need to be able to describe. These include image data and “hierarchical” data sets which are composed of nested arrays of arrays. Both structures are common in some domains but are not yet addressed by the DDI-CDI specification. The use of the DDI-CDI approach is now being investigated, to determine whether the component toolkit for describing data structures types can also encompass these forms. It is anticipated that more such examples will be encountered, but that the same basic approach, based on the role of the datum as the focus of structural description, will allow a consistent model to be created covering a broader range of data types.

Description of Process/Provenance

DDI-CDI provides an implementation of the popular PROV-O vocabulary to describe the kinds of processes which involve data, both at the data set level and at a more fine-grained “variable” level. It also uses ideas from Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN). The intent of the specification is not to provide line-by-line transcriptions of processing code, or to support the recreation of processing environments, but to describe the data and related metadata which are used in the production of data. Because DDI-CDI describes data at a fine-grained level, it can connect data to the various types of processes which operate on it. These processes can be described using other standard models such as the Statistical Data Transformation Language (SDTL) or using proprietary syntaxes.

DDI-CDI provides a framework for describing the overall flow of data and metadata through processes, so that its provenance can be understood not just in general descriptive terms, but at a detailed level. While the DDI-CDI description of process is primarily aimed at describing the processes which have taken place to produce existing data, the use of the model to describe

forward-looking processes for the purposes of process management and reuse is also being considered.

3. Implementation Considerations

DDI-CDI is not intended to be used in a monolithic fashion: users will select those parts of the model which are needed to support a specific function or application. Any specific application using DDI-CDI will select which parts of the model to support and will also choose some target platform and syntax-specific means of doing so. All of this information would be notionally described in an implementation guide. (While DDI-CDI provides a standard XML serialization as a default, there is no requirement that it be used.)

Test implementations have shown that in many cases DDI-CDI would not be authored by hand, in the way that documentation and metadata frequently are, but would be mined from the applications which are performing processes or generated by performing transformations on other (typically domain-specific) metadata formats. In practical terms, the automation of metadata creation is critical to the adoption of DDI-CDI: the granularity of data description and process description DDI-CDI supports would otherwise likely be viewed as prohibitive.

This has the implication that the DDI-CDI model is not intended for direct use by researchers or other end-users of data products. It is a model designed to be deployed in middleware systems which support end-user activities. From the perspective of infrastructure design and implementation, the model can be an important basis for interoperability and reuse of data and metadata. From the end-user perspective, however, it is essentially invisible. (This implication is in line with the sometimes-ignored reality that researchers often rely on a cadre of data managers, archivists, and similar professionals to help them locate, access, and use data as efficiently as possible, allowing them to focus on their research.)

The model is a differentiated model: it addresses the complexity of the subject, describing various data structure types and process. Infrastructure implementers are already dealing with complex models for their data and metadata. Giving them a standard model helps reduce the effort needed to produce the kind of sophisticated infrastructure needed to support data sharing and integration across domain and institutional boundaries by removing the need for the independent development of similar (but non-standard) models.

II. EOSC Cross-Domain Requirements

A. Overview

A generalized model such as DDI-CDI can be implemented to support a wide range of applications. To understand how EOSC can best make use of such a model, we need to consider the possible applications which will be of greatest value in the EOSC data-sharing environment. To do this, it is perhaps easiest to summarize the data-sharing requirements which EOSC will face.

EOSC is a shared infrastructure, and it further anticipates that research data will be shared across domain boundaries, between the various clusters. It must be stressed that this is not the only—possibly not even the most important—data-sharing use case. Many of the issues encountered when sharing data across disciplinary and domain boundaries also occur within domains, especially when they are as broadly defined as they are for the purposes of the clusters in EOSC.

This summary of the EOSC requirements for FAIR data will focus on cross-domain data sharing, but it should be borne in mind that many of the same requirements may exist within clusters where

sharing of disparate types of data occurs. While not specific to DDI-CDI, the emphasis will be on those requirements which are potentially addressed by the use of the DDI-CDI specification.

B. Data Discovery

In any data-sharing scenario data discovery is a prerequisite. Many domains have deployed data catalogues for use within their domains, and many excellent standards. Models, and technologies exist for the purposes of facilitating data discovery. Often, such standards and technologies are based on generic ones for web discovery, specialized for use with data. Examples of this include approaches such as that used by Schema.org and Dublin Core. Others have been specifically designed for use with data: DCAT is perhaps the most important example of this from an EOSC perspective.

When considering what is needed to support data discovery, it is important to bear in mind that – unlike many other digital resources for which people search on the web – the data which is the goal of the search is actually not the digital object which is indexed to support search. When searching for data, you do not perform a google for the number you are looking for – instead, you perform a search on the *metadata* which describes what that number means. While obvious, this has a profound impact on how we search for and discover data: the metadata becomes the predominant consideration.

Many minimal metadata schemes have been described to support search. DataCite’s scheme is a good example of this: a minimal set of fields are offered, with the intention of making it easy for data producers and archives to list their data holdings in catalogues (etc.) Often, such schemes do not provide any information at the detailed level of the variables contained in the data set, but only describe data at the level of a study, experiment, or even data file.

Such schemes are widely adopted because they present a low barrier to entry for those wishing to list their data holdings in a particular catalog. However, this has the consequence that the data becomes visible, but may not be usable, as there may not be sufficient information about it in the required form. There is a second important step in “discovering” data – identifying whether or not it is fit for purpose. While a discovered data set may have the right topical coverage, it may have issues regarding its periodicity or geographical bounding which render it non-useful for the analysis for which it is wanted (to cite a common example). Ideally, such issues are identified early on in the selection of data for reuse.

We can understand the requirements around data discoverability within EOSC as existing on both of these levels: data must be visible – that is, it’s existence must be known – but it must also be *assessable* – that is, enough detailed information about it must be available to assure the researcher that the data is fit for purpose. This is especially important in cases where data is potentially disclosive, and access must be applied for to guarantee that it is not mis-used. It may be annoying and time-consuming to download and wade through publicly available data to determine fitness for purpose, but when the data cannot be easily accessed, the lack of assessability may become a significant barrier to reuse.

Our requirements for data discovery within EOSC can be summarized as:

- (1) Data must be visible to researchers – it’s existence must be known and a general description provided
- (2) Data must be assessable by researchers – it should either be available for exploration and examination by the potential user (publicly available) , be available in a “synthetic” form, or

should have enough detailed accompanying metadata to support a determination of fitness for purpose.

- (3) Data producers and archives should be able to make their data discoverable at the lowest possible cost – minimal cataloguing schemes should be supported because they lower the barriers to entry, even while they may not satisfy user requirements.
- (4) Existing standards, models, and technology approaches should be embraced and supported to the greatest feasible extent – existing and readily available solutions to data discovery will present lower barriers to entry for data producers and archives, although these must also ensure that user requirements in this area are met.

C. Data Integration and Reuse: Cross-Domain Considerations

Once discovered and found fit for purpose, the challenge becomes one of making the data suitable for the analysis which is to be performed. There are several questions which stem from the reuse of data across domain and institutional boundaries which will be addressed in the next section – aspects of data provenance and context – but there are almost always issues around the technical reuse of the data which must be dealt with.

These issues include the transformation of data into a suitable format for the analysis platform, the identification of data which are exactly or approximately equivalent, and the bridging of semantics associated with the data. Different domains have very different cultures and technology tools for data production, management, and analysis, resulting from the nature of the research within that domain. In many cases, data harmonization requires that these differences be understood and accounted for.

The most obvious example of this is seen in how data is structured. In some domains, data is typically collected using sensors. Because sensors produce repeated measurements across time, the data are naturally organized in formats which reflect this, as streams. Streams of data can be easily encoded into files for any given time range by simply arranging the measurements one after another in a “long” file which records each measurement as an event in the order of occurrence. In contrast, data collected from individuals using questionnaires takes a different form: each respondent answers a set of questions, which naturally are formatted with the respondents organized one-per-row and the questions associated with columns in a “rectangular” table containing the data collected at the time the questionnaire was administered. (Other formats are similarly suited to their methods of collection, analysis, etc.)

Within any given technology package used for analysis, it is often simple to go from one such format to another: in packages such as SPSS and Stata, there are commands for transforming data such as that described above. Within the confines of a particular technology environment, the roles played by each individual cell in the table are known, and their equivalents in a different-but-corresponding format can be computed. Within domains, commonly used technology tools are often equipped to understand the formats used by their competitors, such that within a domain’s technology culture data can be reformatted fairly easily.

This type of functionality is far more difficult to achieve across the different technology platforms used in different domains, unless the requisite metadata (that is the role played by the cells in the tables) is understood. Within a given domain, the culture of technology and the nature of the data often result in much of the needed metadata being implicit: no one documents such metadata, because – within that domain – there is no need to.

Issues around data management become important. Much is made of the ability to cite data with persistent identifiers, and this is without question important. However, such citations are typically made at the level of data sets or data files. If there is a requirement to describe individual cells, and the roles they play, their identification is assumed to be the identifier of their data set, qualified by whatever identification is used to differentiate cells within the data set or file.

An issue arises here because different data formats employ different systems of identification. In a rectangular table, the unit identifier (the “row number”) can be qualified by the column identifier (i.e. data variable) to uniquely identify a cell within the data set. If the same data is expressed in a “long” data file, as a series of collection events, these two data points are no longer sufficient to guarantee that a cell has been uniquely identified. While the understanding of how “keys” – compound identifiers – function in different data structures exists, often an explicit description of how they operate within a specific data set is lacking at the time of discovery, and must be determined through an examination of the data in question.

If we need to exchange data across domain boundaries and technology platforms, we will need to transform data into useful formats. To do this, we need to understand the roles played by cells (in our example, whether they are functioning as identifiers). This information – fine-grained structural metadata – must be known. Today, such problems are solved manually – for each data set, researchers manipulate the incoming data until it is in a useful form. The cost of such data “wrangling” is significant: “As a rule of thumb, in a data analysis project, data cleansing of poor quality data can take up to 80% of the total effort.”⁴ .

In addition to these structural challenges, semantics are typically different across (and even within) domains. A great deal of effort has gone (and continues to go) into the formalization of domain semantics in ontologies and vocabularies, and there are many technology solutions devoted to solving these challenges. Typically, these focus on the idea of a concept (as seen in the popular SKOS ontology).

It is possible today to describe the equivalence (even the degree of equivalence) between two concepts, helping us to bridge the divide between two data sets. This is not, however, sufficient. When it comes to describing data, concepts play a wide variety of different roles. A concept used to define the characteristic of a unit of study is not the same as the concept used to define a categorical meaning which expresses a measurement of that concept.

For example, I may use a concept of “sex” to describe a variable (that is, a characteristic of my unit, a person): my fields will have values corresponding to the concepts “male,” “female, “ etc., functioning as categorical measurements of that characteristic. In another data set, the variables might use the concepts “male” and “female” to define characteristics of the population and may contain measures which are counts or ratios. This is an importance difference when integrating the data. Unless the structural use of a concept is understood in relation to the structure of a data set—and the other concepts employed by that structure—a simple equivalence between the concepts is often not enough to inform data reuse or automate transformations.

Again, such problems are most often today solved manually. It is only through the combination of formal semantic mappings, and a knowledge of how concepts are used within the data structure, that it would be possible to automate such solutions.

⁴ Cost-benefit analysis for FAIR research data. EU publication, 2019-01-16 - <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d375368c-1a0a-11e9-8d04-01aa75ed71a1>

The requirements we see for EOSC in this description of data reuse and integration can be described as:

- (1) The metadata available for a reusable data set should include a description of its overall structure.
- (2) It should also include specific information about the roles played by individual data points/cells within that structure. Often this information is already implicitly available and should be expressed in an explicit form. (See the UKDA SERL example, below.)
- (3) Formal semantic definitions (and mappings between the schemes they use) should be made available for the purposes of best utilizing this structural information.

D. Provenance and Context for Data Reuse

Reuse of data across domain and institutional boundaries also faces another set of challenges: what is the context within which the data was collected, and which establishes it as useful? Such information is often referred to as “provenance” metadata, and the term covers a broad range of topics.

To give one example, the W3 Provenance Incubator Group defines data provenance as:

...a record that describes entities and processes involved in producing and delivering or otherwise influencing that resource. Provenance provides a critical foundation for assessing authenticity, enabling trust, and allowing reproducibility. Provenance assertions are a form of contextual metadata and can themselves become important records with their own provenance.

Researchers will often have questions regarding the collectors of the data, and the tools and methods employed. In some domains, the techniques used for sampling a population to be measured are of acute interest. In other domains, such methods cannot be used because the data is drawn from sources such as administrative registers which give the researcher no control over the breadth of data collection, or any of the biases which may be inherent in how it was compiled.

Issues around funding are often important, as are the identities of the researchers. Many aspects of provenance touch on issues of data quality, as the research questions driving an analysis will view different aspects of provenance as positive or negative depending on what they seek to measure. Efforts to ensure that data on sensitive topics is non-disclosive can result in a degree of “damage” to the data and must also be understood.

Not least important, the tools and processes used to collect, clean, and harmonize/integrate data must be described. In domains where sensors are used, the model of the sensor and many aspects of its use are significant. In research employing questionnaires, the wording of questions may impact data. The techniques used to “clean” data (e.g., the trimming of outliers, anonymization, imputation) may also be of interest. Interpretive re-coding of the raw data – as in the case of open-ended questions or “notes” fields in registers – can have an impact on what is reflected in the data.

This type of provenance metadata is typically addressed in two ways: using narrative descriptions of the overall data collection and processing effort or environment, and by the presentation of relevant artefacts involved in the process (executable code from a statistical processing package, a copy of the questionnaire used in a survey, etc.) Often, such artefacts are less meaningful outside a domain than within it: they may rely on access to software tools which are not familiar to a researcher who wants to reuse the data. Similarly, narrative descriptions of provenance may be less directly useful

because they are written within the context of a domain's literature and community, and important aspects of these may be unfamiliar to the researcher wanting to reuse the data. Even within domains, it is often the case that sufficient provenance information is lacking to accompany the data offered for reuse by archives and other data disseminators.

It is simplistic to assume that any given data set comes from a single source in a monolithic fashion, especially under the conditions of modern research. Data goes through many different stages as it is produced, analyzed, and readied for dissemination, and it is often impossible to form a clear picture of exactly what steps any given data set (or portion of a data set) has gone through before being presented for reuse.

A fairly recent development here are attempts to standardize provenance metadata in a generic fashion, meaningful across domain boundaries. The W3C's PROV Ontology has provided a basis for establishing accessible provenance information which is machine-readable, and several different standards have emerged for describing processing, sensors, etc.

Ideally, provenance metadata should be rich enough to support the replication and reproduction of findings, and (to the greatest extent possible) in a machine-actionable fashion. This may seem like an impossibility, but the importance of replication cannot be underestimated, as we have seen in recent days over the publications in the medical literature on COVID and questions about the data used.

Perhaps the best-known recent example concerned the retraction of articles in the journals *Lancet* and *The New England Journal of Medicine*, as described recently in *Science*⁵.

Data provenance may not seem to be critical to researchers at the time they perform their analysis (although it often does), but it can have serious impacts on the subsequent usability of their research findings especially in secondary analysis.

The requirements for EOSC are these:

- (1) Provenance metadata should be provided for data which is intended for sharing/reuse at the level of the data collection/generation.
- (2) Provenance metadata should be provided for data at a granular (e.g., variable) level, describing specific processes and tools used in its collection and preparation.
- (3) To the extent possible, provenance metadata should be made available in generic forms which are machine-readable and comprehensible outside of their domain of origination.
- (4) Replication and reproduction of findings should be supported to the greatest extent possible, and ideally in a fashion which is supported by automation and the machine-actionability of provenance metadata.

E. Automation and Issues of Scale

When we consider the FAIR data vision, and how this might become a reality within the EOSC context, we need to consider the current state of play around FAIR data (and metadata) publication, and contrast that with probable dynamics which might result from the establishment of a more-

⁵ Science - <https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2020/06/two-elite-medical-journals-retract-coronavirus-papers-over-data-integrity-questions>

effective data-sharing infrastructure. As with many things, the benefits realized through enhanced data-sharing will also bring with them their own challenges.

FAIR itself enjoys its current popularity from the undeniable demand that data be a reusable resource, within domains, but also between them. The demand, however, does not change the fact that this type of data-sharing is both difficult and costly. EOSC anticipates that these burdens can be lessened, making research less expensive and difficult by (among other things) facilitating data reuse. A necessary aspect of this is metadata reuse.

The degree to which EOSC is successful in this endeavor will directly translate into one of the biggest challenges which the research community will then face: the sheer volume of potentially useable data. Data-hungry approaches in both the research sphere and the technology sphere are becoming more common, and the appetite for more data is a pressing reality. Supplying that appetite is more challenging.

Much attention within the FAIR community has been focused on data discovery, that being the first piece of the problem which must be solved. In relative terms, however, the volume of metadata required to facilitate data discovery is small when compared to the amount of metadata needed to enable other parts of the FAIR vision, notably interoperability and reuse.

Regardless, the fact that cross-domain and cross-institutional data use is relatively metadata-intensive, combined with the increased volume of sharable data, presents an obvious challenge: one of scale. EOSC will need to support a volume of metadata production which is well beyond what is commonly done today, and the more effective EOSC is in sharing data, the bigger the problem grows.

This challenge comes with a set of solutions, however, and one which is very much in line with the data-hungry approaches in research which have given rise to it: scalability through automation. With increasingly effective AI and “big data” tools at our disposal, we can – assuming our metadata is machine-actionable – begin to use those approaches not only for analyzing data, but also for sharing it and for capturing and sharing the metadata on which its use depends.

The idea that huge volumes of detailed metadata will be captured manually, in the way that data is often documented today, is not a viable one. The cost of manual “after-the-fact” metadata is prohibitive, to say nothing of the culture around scientific research and funding which has led to our current state of insufficient documentation and shareability of data.

The metadata which we require exists inside the system and processes which produce, manage, and disseminate it, however. This offers a way to meet the demand without a huge amount of manual intervention: machines can be equipped to externalize this information in a shareable form alongside the data as part of their functioning. This idea of machine-generated metadata – and especially as facilitated by the use of machine learning and other AI approaches – provides a way forward in the face of the growth in demand for metadata.

This presents a further requirement: a suitable set of agreed protocols and metadata standards will need to be established, so that the metadata not only exists, but that it does so in way which is shareable.

In many particulars, standards exist for this type of metadata. Within domains, there are often useful standards for sharing data and metadata effectively (i.e., DDI-Codebook and DDI-Lifecycle for the social, behavioural and economic sciences; the OMOP Common data Model for clinical records; many, many different domain ontologies described in RDF/OWL, etc.). There are also some

standards which are cross-domain in scope (i.e., DCAT for data catalogues, SKOS for concept systems, etc.) Critical here are systems of persistent identification which have been established for data. (These are heavily emphasized in the FAIR literature, and rightly so, for both data and metadata.)

Many protocols exist for the exchange of relevant data and metadata, including many of the standards produced by the W3C related to RDF, as well as some more-focused ideas such as the proposals for FAIR Digital Objects.

There are also standards for describing the processing and workflows involved in the data lifecycle, useful for replication and understanding provenance, although many of these approaches are of recent vintage (the International FAIR Convergence Symposium in December 2020 held an interesting session on “FAIR Data Provenance” during which many of these were presented.)

What is missing, however, is a generic way of describing data structures and data processing in a way which allows for a generic, machine-actionable use at the level of each individual data point across the span of its existence, and across use in different contexts. This requires not only access to a low-level understanding of the internals of a data set, but also an understanding (even at a formal level) of the data set’s specific relationship to other data sets which may contribute to it.

This need can be illustrated by considering the following case:

It is possible today to search in a data catalogue and learn that a wanted set of data exists. It is likely possible to obtain an identifier for that data set, along with enough information to select it from among the others available (based on temporal, spatial, and topical coverage, etc.) It may be possible to determine that the metadata associated with that data is encoded according to a domain specification, which might or might not support machine-actionable operations on it.

If that domain specification is not understood, or does not provide machine-actionable metadata, then the data is not immediately useful. Its structural and internal system of identification for its components remains unknown.

If the data is based on other data, external to the discovered data set, that may also be critically important in its use (i.e., a discovered data set contains a value computed from other data sources, leading to inconsistencies or demanding validation during data cleaning before use). The identification and retrieval of such data by a machine is generally not possible today.

In order to meet the needs which EOSC faces in terms of scale, machine-actionable metadata is required which will provide a “lingua franca” between systems for this information. Further, because data are not static, and are reused in many ways in different contexts, the ability to understand the path of a given datum is required: knowing that a subset of a dataset came from an identified source can be useful, but unless the metadata are sufficient to define exactly which subset was reused, then the operation of machines for many important processes (provenance, replication/reproduction of findings, etc.) is not possible.

A standard which provides this holistic description of data as it is created and used, at a granular level as well as a “data set” level, is required to complete the metadata set.

III. General Comments: EOSC/DDI-CDI Implementation Examples

DDI-CDI was developed to fill some of the gaps in the coverage of the standards available to meet the requirements described above. The following examples have been selected not to provide a survey of these requirements, but to explore the specifics of how DDI-CDI could contribute to a solution. Each example will illustrate, using a real-world case, salient aspects of the role DDI-CDI could play, and for which there is currently no standards-based tool available. The examples are described on the basis of conversations with experts in the specific field. (The meetings are listed in a separate document, “The Role of DDI-CDI in EOSC: Report on Activities”.)

As DDI-CDI is a relatively new specification, and will be released for production use in the summer of 2021), it is still possible for EOSC to recommend changes to the specification to better meet the needs which it might place on the implementation of DDI-CDI, and some of the recommendations in this report will outline possibilities here.

Please note that in this report we use the term “examples” in a broad way: these are real world cases that allow us to understand and present aspects of the problem space and not necessarily detailed use cases or implementations.

The examples provided cover a range of subjects and explore various aspects of DDI-CDI implementation. Implementations within specific communities, focused on particular data publication and exchange scenarios are provided (the UKDA example, the European Social Survey Hierarchical example) while others look more into potential software implementations (the Dataverse example) or the alignment with other standards and initiatives. Each example will focus on a specific set of issues and suggest potential solutions in practical terms, appropriate to the example and the technological capabilities of the organization.

Notionally, the examples are organized to show first how specific problems can be solved regarding issues around cross-domain data sharing and integration, and then to fit the envisioned use of DDI-CDI within the overall frame of European metadata practices and the emerging EOSC framework more specifically. The later examples will focus more on related standards initiatives and their use within EOSC which would be significant in relation to the use of DDI-CDI.

List of examples:

- UK Data Archive: Granular Metadata for Cross-Domain Integration
- Dataverse: Data Repository Capturing and Providing Metadata in a Lingua Franca to Support Cross-Domain Integration
- European Social Survey Multilevel Application: Efficiency Improvements for Survey Data Integrated with National and Regional Data from Other Domains
- The ALPHA Network and INSPIRE: Integration of Data from Clinical Systems and Questionnaires Highlight Differences in Domains which Require Context/Provenance Information
- DDI-CDI and the FAIR Ecosystem
- DDI-CDI and EOSC: The EOSC Interoperability Framework and the FAIRsFAIR Proposal on Integration of Metadata Catalogues

IV. UK Data Archive: Granular Metadata for Cross-Domain Integration

A. Background

The UK Data Archive (UKDA) is an archive for the social and economic sciences and has long been an active member of CESSDA and the DDI community, regularly engaging in projects involving not only economic and social research in the UK, but also in collaboration with other domain groups, including environmental and health sciences.

For our purposes, UKDA typifies some of the requirements emerging from projects in Europe regarding cross-domain data use. The involvement of the archive in initiatives such as the recently launched Population Research UK (PRUK) project⁶ demonstrates the cross-domain nature of some emerging research in the UK.

At a more technical level, they have begun work on a position paper entitled “Building a Use Case for EOSC” (Bell, Darren, L’Hours, Hervé, Jonson, Jon, 'Building a Use Case for EOSC'⁷, unpublished/draft position paper shared with the authors which highlights a number of the practical issues which face implementers when they attempt to realize the vision established in the EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF). Some of these issues can be addressed through the use of DDI-CDI, which is mentioned in the paper as perhaps the only extant solution to the issues around structural interoperability. Some of the position paper’s arguments will be summarised, as they clearly state the issues faced by the providers of FAIR data in light of emerging demands in research.

To further illustrate these requirements, we will look at the Smart Energy Research Lab (SERL), involving UKDA, in which survey data, meter readings of energy use, and climate data are combined for research purposes. Data coming from different sources and with very different structures illustrate the metadata needed to assemble useful analysis data sets. While the SERL project is housed entirely at the UKDA, it is easy to see—as evidenced by the PRUK and as highlighted in the EOSC Use Case document—that such an integration of data needs to be possible across organizational boundaries.

It should be noted that we discuss the SERL example here to illustrate the requirements around data integration which will need to be addressed in an EOSC context where such integration is performed across domain and institutional boundaries in an “on-demand” fashion: the value of SERL today is in the presentation of an integrated data set from which many different useful subsets can be derived, in the absence of the envisioned EOSC infrastructure.

B. "Building a Use Case for EOSC"

The position paper, ‘Building a Use Case for EOSC’, presents a coherent statement of the both the need for and the difficulties faced by the purveyors of FAIR data for the modern research community. At the time of writing, the position paper has not been published in any form, so we will include several relevant quotations from it here.

Regarding the requirements, it states:

Research at its core depends on data, its availability, discovery, integrity and the capability for it to be analysed. In the early 21st century research is being undertaken on data that:

⁶ Population Research UK - <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/population-research-uk/>

⁷ Building a Use Case for EOSC - https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uTrTFHXyhuNUIAKHEdtk2cRnLUi0xjUHfFiLyl_SRQ/edit

- *is more complex,*
- *is of an order of magnitude larger,*
- *is coming from more sources,*
- *requires more sophisticated analysis and*
- *must also confront the issues of privacy and confidentiality.*

This is a good summary of the high-level requirements. The position paper also mentions some further detail regarding the interplay between semantic integration and structural integration, very much in line with how these concerns are separated in the DDI-CDI specification:

The EOSC IF rightly places an emphasis on the importance of semantic interoperability - for how else could climatologists communicate with social scientists? The mechanisms for ontology cross-walks are well understood, relatively mature and in RDF, have an almost irreducibly granular way to represent and exchange semantics. However, there are still real blockers associated with structural interoperability.

Asserting that your data object (it could be an SPSS file or an XML representation of an SPSS file) is "FAIR" is fine but it may still may not be readily interoperable in the sense that two FAIR objects with different schema, even open and commonly understood schema, cannot be immediately combined for cross-domain analysis without some kind of structural crosswalk, which may not even be possible depending on the underlying data paradigm being used for each object.

The focus of DDI-CDI on the structural interoperability between disparate data, and its importance in addition to semantic interoperability is significant here. But the position paper further states what is perhaps the most critical point: metadata must be sufficiently granular in its structural descriptions:

The other barrier to such ontology cross-walks is the lack of available descriptive metadata held at the right level. Often it is held at a dataset level or implied through labels on data items, either of which are neither usefully machine readable or indeed actionable.

Files have (largely) been the basic unit of storage (and dissemination) for research data. Changes in data governance, particularly in the dissemination of biomedical and administrative data, as well as where survey microdata is being analyzed in conjunction with genetic data is shifting the requirement to be able to access individual data items.

The centrality DDI-CDI places on the datum as the focus of its metadata agrees with this understanding. As we cross domain boundaries, the need for this more granular focus on the "data item" (a datum in DDI-CDI terms) is made clear.

The requirements can be further understood when we consider how requirements around non-disclosure and data confidentiality intersect with the "data set"- (or file-) level metadata so commonly encountered today.

In a section titled "Data Poisoning" the position paper describes the following important scenario:

... a dataset containing fifty variables may have two "risky" variables and hence the whole dataset will be classed as secure, forcing restrictions on its access, which may then involve a large amount of human mediated administration. A much more flexible way forward would be the ability to automatically subset data based on levels of disclosure. For example, from a fictional GUI, a researcher might choose to take only forty-eight variables from our fictional dataset above, on the basis that they could begin to analyze those immediately, as low risk.

Such obviously useful functionality is simply not available at the moment, as the structural metadata is not in place to support such operations...

The importance of managing data at a granular level is thus highlighted in the pragmatic terms of an institution concerned with the dissemination of FAIR data for research purposes. It is significant that the authors of this paper are implementers and understand very directly what metadata is available and how machine-actionable it is in practical terms.

(While the paper also comments further on data access, this is beyond the scope of what DDI-CDI is intended to do. It can expose the data at a granular level for fine-grained access control but does not itself manage this aspect of FAIR sharing.)

The position paper goes on to make further analyses and to recommend some approaches within an EOSC context that go beyond the scope of this report, but it is significant that the paper provides such a detailed description of the need for metadata and systems to have a more granular focus on data, to meet emerging research needs.

C. A Cross-Domain Example: Assembling a Data Set for Analysis

1. Overview

The following example is taken from an ongoing project, the Smart Energy Research Lab (SERL)⁸ lead by the UCL Energy Institute, and involving the UKDA, among other partners. The example illustrates the technical aspects of integrating data which exists in disparate forms: it will serve to show the specific types of structural metadata which are needed to perform such linking, and to illustrate how DDI-CDI can help to provide a mechanism for performing such linking. The data examples given are synthetic and are provided to show the structure of the data but are not actual data on actual cases. (Examples of the data and metadata were kindly provided by Darren Bell of UKDA and the other partners in the project.)

The scenario combines data coming from three different sources: temperature readings are measured and reported across the UK; smart meter readings are taken for customers to determine the household energy usage for billing purposes and provided for research by the utility; and a sampling of customers have agreed to answer survey questions regarding their energy use.

The linkages between these data are straightforward: survey respondents belong to metered households, and these exist within known locations of the UK where temperature readings are recorded. Structurally, however, it can be understood that these data assume different forms.

⁸ Smart Energy Research Lab (SERL) - <https://serl.ac.uk/>

While SERL is providing researchers with an integrated data set, complete with the information needed to link between these disparate data, this is a before-the-fact activity which has been performed manually and documented. The point of looking at such an example is to envision how an integrated data set could be created in an on-demand fashion by researchers if the providers of the various data sets had access to the necessary metadata, and to show to what extent this process could be automated.

To do this, we will show what linkages are necessary, and look at how these were realized by the SERL integration. Following that, we will consider how DDI-CDI could express this information in a standard form, such that a similar integration could be performed—given access to the data—without the same high degree of manual intervention.

2. The Data Sets

Three different data sets are involved in this research: the temperature readings, the smart meter readings, and the participant responses to surveys. We will briefly show each.

Temperature Data

Below is a view of the temperature data, taken from the Copernicus/ECMWF Hourly Reanalysis Data (ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1979 to present (copernicus.eu)⁹).

⁹ Climate Copernicus - <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp%23!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>

Sample Climate dataset - 2928 rows for 2 grid cells relevant to two households/participants
 Real dataset has c. 30 million rows

gridCell	analysisDate	utcDateTime	temperature_2_metres_K	temperature_2_metres_C
38_18	2018-09-04	2018-09-04T14:00:00Z	284.15	11.96
38_18	2018-09-04	2018-09-04T15:00:00Z	284.18	11.99
38_18	2018-09-04	2018-09-04T16:00:00Z	284.21	12.02
38_18	2018-09-04	2018-09-04T17:00:00Z	284.22	12.03
38_18	2018-09-04	2018-09-04T18:00:00Z	284.18	11.99
38_18	2018-09-04	2018-09-04T19:00:00Z	284.16	11.97
38_18	2018-09-04	2018-09-04T20:00:00Z	284.17	11.98
38_18	2018-09-04	2018-09-04T21:00:00Z	284.14	11.95
38_18	2018-09-04	2018-09-04T22:00:00Z	284.11	11.92
38_18	2018-09-04	2018-09-04T23:00:00Z	284.10	11.91
38_18	2018-09-05	2018-09-05T00:00:00Z	284.10	11.91
38_18	2018-09-05	2018-09-05T01:00:00Z	284.08	11.89

This is captured in a structure typical of such measurements: the “gridCell” column holds an identifier for the geographical area, accompanied by columns providing date and time fields, and a pair of measurements, one in degrees Kelvin and the other in Centigrade. Each measurement can be uniquely identified by a combination of these fields: region + date-time + measurement (Kelvin or Centigrade).

This data is captured and reported on an hourly basis across Great Britain, according to a geographical scheme which organizes the regions into meaningful areas for the climate scientists who primarily use the data.

Smart Meter Data

The smart meter data is reported by the Data Communications Company (DCC)¹⁰, a business which handles the provision of smart meter data to the various players in the energy field. The data is reported at midnight to SERL for the preceding day’s readings, for those customers who have agreed to participate in the study.

The data is structured in a format which is more complex—smart meters take many different types of readings—but which is structurally similar to the temperature data:

¹⁰ Data Communications Company (DCC) - <https://www.smartdcc.co.uk/>

Real dataset approx 1.7 billion rows (13k participants; around 5 devices per participant; 48 readings;

PUPRN	Read_date	Read_date_time	HH	Valid_read	Elec_import	Elec_act_i	Elec_act_e
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T14:00:00Z	28	TRUE	TRUE	103	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T14:30:00Z	29	TRUE	TRUE	31	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T15:00:00Z	30	TRUE	TRUE	38	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T15:30:00Z	31	TRUE	TRUE	32	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T16:00:00Z	32	TRUE	TRUE	42	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T16:30:00Z	33	TRUE	TRUE	74	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T17:00:00Z	34	TRUE	TRUE	67	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T17:30:00Z	35	TRUE	TRUE	63	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T18:00:00Z	36	TRUE	TRUE	185	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T18:30:00Z	37	TRUE	TRUE	135	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T19:00:00Z	38	TRUE	TRUE	44	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T19:30:00Z	39	TRUE	TRUE	34	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T20:00:00Z	40	TRUE	TRUE	40	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T20:30:00Z	41	TRUE	TRUE	27	1
33PAUAP3	2018-08-01	2018-03-01T21:00:00Z	42	TRUE	TRUE	15	1

The columns extending off to the right of the image above include a series of 17 fields for each record. The nature of these can be seen in the rows of this extract from the data dictionary:

Field	Derived	Description	Unit	Class	Example value
PUPRN		Pseudonymised participant identifier	NA	character	1VUXXXF1
Read_date_effective		Date of read (same as date of Read_date_time unless read taken at midnight, then the previous day since data is for half hour on previous day)	%Y-%m-%d	Date	2019-11-01
Read_date_time		Time read taken (UTC)	%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S	POSIXct, POSIXt	2019-11-0200:00:00
HH		Half-hour identifier between 1 and 48 (NA if not on the half hour)	NA	integer	48
Valid_read_time	TRUE	FALSE if read time is not on the hour or half hour, otherwise TRUE	NA	logical	TRUE
Elec_import_exists	TRUE	TRUE if electricity import meter exists in the inventory, otherwise FALSE	NA	logical	TRUE
Elec_act_imp_hh_Wh		Half-hourly electricity active import read	Wh	integer	109
Elec_act_imp_flag	TRUE	Half-hourly electricity active import error flag	NA	numeric	-2
Elec_react_imp_hh_varh		Half-hourly electricity reactive import read	varh	integer	15
Elec_react_imp_flag	TRUE	Half-hourly electricity reactive import error flag	NA	numeric	1
Elec_export_exists	TRUE	TRUE if electricity export meter exists in the inventory, otherwise FALSE	NA	logical	FALSE
Elec_act_exp_hh_Wh		Half-hourly electricity active export read	Wh	integer	65
Elec_act_exp_flag	TRUE	Half-hourly electricity active export error flag	NA	numeric	-4
Elec_react_exp_hh_varh		Half-hourly electricity reactive export read	varh	integer	14
Elec_react_exp_flag	TRUE	Half-hourly electricity reactive export error flag	NA	numeric	2
Gas_exists	TRUE	TRUE if gas meter exists in the inventory, otherwise FALSE	NA	logical	TRUE
Gas_hh_m3		Half-hourly gas import read	m3	numeric	0.244
Gas_hh_Wh	TRUE	Half-hourly gas import read in Wh using standard	Wh	numeric	2737.835

The first column in the smart meter data has a pseudo-anonymized participant ID number, followed by the date and time information. Following this, each of the 17 fields have unique names (the column headers) giving an indication of what the measurement (or supporting information) is in each case: a measurement regarding the electric usage, gas usage, whether there was an error in the reading, etc.

As with the temperature data, a similar set of information forms the unique identifier of any given measurement or related field: the participant ID + date-time + measurement. Note that there are

dependencies between some measurements: they act to inform the use of another column in the record at that time for that participant.

It should be noted that meter readings may be every half-hour or hour on a regular schedule, or may be more intermittent, and that fields describing the nature of each meter reading are provided.

Questionnaire Data

The data coming from the questionnaire is perhaps simpler in format: each survey participant is recruited by SERL to participate in a wave of the study, in which they will answer a series of between 30 and 39 questions (30 questions are generally applicable – the remaining 9 depend on earlier answers and may not need a response).

The questions cover a range of topics regarding the household which is consuming energy (use of central heating, detached/semi-detached, number and age of inhabitants, etc.) as well as some additional questions dealing with behaviours (leaving windows open, etc.) and also perceptions of financial well-being and home ownership.

The resulting data set is structured in a rectangular table, where each row is identified by a participant ID number, and each answered question is stored in a column specific to that question. The questionnaire does have some “check all that apply” questions, which complicate this structure slightly by adding additional fields, but the relationship between the survey questions and the stored responses is straightforward, and does not involve the interpretation of any complicated, open-ended textual responses (although some questions use the relatively limited “Other – please specify” construction).

To give a sense of the kinds of questions asked, here are a few taken at random from the questionnaire:

Before we contacted you about this study, did you know you had a smart meter?

To what extent, if at all, would you say that having a smart meter has affected the way you use gas or electricity in your accommodation?

What type of central heating does your accommodation have? By central heating we mean a central system that generates heat for multiple rooms.

Do any of your standalone heaters have their own source of fuel (e.g. from logs, coal or bottled gas)?

If your accommodation is unoccupied for more than a day or so, how often will your household adjust the heating controls to ensure the heating either won't, or is much less likely to come on?

How much effort, if any, would you say your household makes to limit or reduce the amount of gas or electricity used?

What type of accommodation do you live in?

How many other households do you share with at the moment?

In order to uniquely identify a cell in the resulting table, you need to know the participant ID number, and the name of the field. Because each data set contains only responses from a single

wave, the date and time is implicit in the data set being considered (each respondent completes one questionnaire per wave.)

In order to produce an integrated data set suitable for analysis, SERL further provides “summary tables” for each participant which give the linking between these data sets. The following diagram shows how this is done:

Dataset relationships

This summary table (“PARTICIPANTS” in the diagram) associates the participant ID number (PUPRN) with the geographic region used by the temperature data (gridCell).

Note that there are many typical issues encountered when analyzing this data: the street address of each participant must be mapped to the climate region, and the temporal aspects must be handled: a single survey response correlates to a large number of temperature and meter readings.

The key to making this data useful for researcher lies in being able to create these linkages, which relies on the ability to associate records and the individual fields within them to some unit of study, across several sources of data.

If a researcher wants to study how households behave at different temperatures as regards their energy use, they need to organize a dataset by households, with some corresponding indication of the energy consumption and the temperature. The organization of the analysis data set will be dependent on the research question and will be determined by the researchers on a project-by-project basis. What is almost universally true, however, is that, in order to produce the desired analysis data set, access will be required to the individual records in all of the data sources.

In the example given, the unique identifiers for each cell are made up of a unit identifier (region or participant ID), a temporal component, and a field identifier. In each of our data sets, these pieces of information will vary from source to source, including where in the structure they are stored. To find this information, human analysis of each data set is required.

Once these aspects of the data have been determined, the process of linking the data (in this example, associating the participant IDs with the region identifiers) can begin, and the processing needed to handle temporal issues can be conducted.

3. How Does DDI-CDI Describe This Information?

DDI-CDI provides a generic model for describing exactly this type of information. It gives a basic model for each of four major types of data structures (wide, long, key-value, and multidimensional) and then describes the fields within them from both a logical/conceptual and physical perspective. The logical description of data fields includes what role a particular field plays in terms of identifying

the records and gives an indication of the dependencies between fields within a record. (These roles vary across the four described types.)

In our example, all of the data sets are similar, in that each record on any given row of the table contains a set of measurements. Each table has a different set of fields which are required to identify the unit of measurement, however: temperature readings for a given region on an hourly basis, meter readings for a given household on a half-hourly basis, or household survey responses on a once-per-wave basis.

These combinations were shown above. The DDI-CDI description provides a number of standard descriptions which are needed to support use of the data:

1. It describes the structure of the data set, and indicates what fields are needed to compose an identifier.
2. It establishes a formal description of each column in the table as a “variable,” which associates its representation (data type, classification/code list, etc.) with the values that may be used to populate it.
3. It assigns a role (identifier or measure) to each of the variables within the structure of the data set.
4. In DDI-CDI you can have fields which provide an enumeration of the possible measures required to disambiguate between the cells in a record (often this is not needed, because the list of variables itself is sufficient to determine what a particular cell is measuring). However, this does not apply in the example taken from UKDA SERL.

In our first SERL dataset, we know that we have a “wide” data set with a series of five variables:

1. Region (gridCell)
2. Date
3. Time
4. Temperature in degrees Kelvin
5. Temperature in degrees Celsius

Each cell can be identified by a combination of four fields, one of which indicates the type of the measurement wanted (Kelvin or Celsius). Our identifiers for each measurement unit include a value from the first three columns. For the unit thus specified—a region at a given point in time—we can select one of the two available measurements.

DDI-CDI performs the task of describing the available fields in the data set in a standard way, and assigning them roles (as identifiers, as measurements) and mapping these to the names found in the specific data set. With this information, a computer program knows enough to process each cell in relation to the entire data set in an appropriate way.

The second SERL dataset, the smart meter data, is almost identical, except that the number of measures for each unit is much larger (17 for each one) and the units are households (participant ID number) qualified by time.

In our third SERL dataset, the questionnaire responses—because the data set contains data for only a single wave—time itself is not needed to disambiguate cells. The unit identifier (participant ID

number) is sufficient to separate the records from one another, at which point all that is needed is to know which of the available variables is wanted for a specific measure.

DDI-CDI also describes (to some extent) the dependencies between variables when they act to qualify each other: an error code variable in a meter reading will inform the value found in the variable containing the meter reading of energy use, etc.

Once we are able to identify each cell in a table, and understand how they relate to form records, it is possible to begin processing the data automatically.

Some issues are not solved by simple identification, however. If we wish to generate a table used to link our data sets (the summary table shown above), then we would need access to something which could perform the crosswalk between the values we have found in our separate data sets. Such a crosswalk might be a known mapping between two standard classifications or code lists (as for geographic regions and postal codes) or might require algorithmic processing (e.g., probabilistic record matching). DDI-CDI is able to describe the processes to which these data sets would be subjected to perform such a mapping, typically with external references to the specific processing code which performed the task (or, if manual, a human-readable description of it). Such references tie the processes performed to the specific data sets and metadata which they consume, and in themselves are a potentially valuable resource for machine action around provenance and replication/reproduction of findings.

DDI-CDI does not solve issues of access control or disclosure, but it does provide a fine-grained description of the data and metadata on which access control can be administered. The access control administration can refer to each single item by its globally unique persistent identifier. The DDI-CDI design does not address that problem specifically, but it does recognize that access control exercised only at the level of entire data sets will subject them to the “data poisoning” described in the preceding section.

4. Conclusions

If we are to imagine an infrastructure where any discovered data set was accompanied by a DDI-CDI description of how its cells could be uniquely identified within its native context, then we can understand that several other problems become more tractable. The manual integration of data sets becomes less arduous: yes, mappings between needed identification systems to establish linkages across data sets must be created, but all of the analysis which frames this task can be performed automatically. The vocabularies involved in such a mapping are directly referenced, so that this task can be immediately understood (and, possibly, have pre-existing solutions applied to it). If others have performed the same integration before, such a process can have been recorded, and reproduced programmatically using the DDI-CDI formalization of the process, supported by whatever processing code was used.

It is clear that DDI-CDI alone will not solve all of the problems around data sharing, but it does solve some of the basic structural ones. Perhaps more important, it provides a structural frame within which other solutions to problems of access control and semantic mapping can become more powerful and efficient.

V. Dataverse: Data Repository Capturing and Providing Metadata in a Lingua Franca to Support Cross-Domain Integration

A. Background

The Dataverse Project is an initiative dating back to 2006 for the development of an open-source data repository software which would be useful across scientific domains. Based on earlier developments at Harvard University, Dataverse now has significant support not only in North America but also in Europe. Two of the largest Dataverse implementations are located in the Netherlands' Data Archiving and Network Services (DANS) and at the University of Tromsø in Norway (<https://dataverse.no/dataverse/tgo>) and it is used in many other European countries and elsewhere across the globe.

Dataverse is an example of a widely adopted open-source project being maintained and enhanced by a very active community and over 100 contributors from around the globe. The Dataverse Project holds regular meetings to prioritize and implement desired features and maintain the product. Similar products include DSpace and CKAN, although Dataverse is perhaps enjoying greater popularity among the European data archives which are members of the CESSDA ERIC (and SSHOC). Coming out of the social sciences world (the initial developments were made by the Institute for Quantitative Social Science at Harvard), Dataverse is well-known within the SBE sciences, and is now used across a wide range of disciplines (i.e., biology, astronomy) but is intended for use in any domain, and has been implemented across a range of different ones.

B. Core Functionality

Dataverse is primarily used by data libraries and archives as a place where data can be held and easily made available to potential secondary users. It is not intended to be an end-to-end solution, but a back-end repository for the applications built by user institutions. As such, it provides open application programming interfaces (APIs) for integration with other systems.

Basic functions include depositing of data and related material, search and discovery functions, and retrieval of data and related materials. It can be used in different ways: as the core of a managed archive, as the repository for a self-archiving solution, and in many other ways. Dataverse often forms the core of a data cataloguing system, which also makes the catalogued contents directly available to users.¹¹

Dataverse provides support for data citation and assigns persistent identifiers to its contents, typically Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), as provided by DataCite. In this way, it is well-aligned with the FAIR principles around persistent identification, at least at the data set level.

Like almost all similar repository software packages, Dataverse is based on the concept of data sets, in which the main focus of management is a collection of data used for a single purpose, in which a given data set is found, accessed and downloaded. It is an archive, rather than a data warehouse, and its functionality and organisation of data and metadata reflects this intended or assumed use.

One of the core features of the Dataverse design, and one that is of importance here, is the separation made between the data itself and the relevant metadata. Dataverse treats metadata as a

¹¹ Several Dataverse repositories are linked to from the Wikipedia page on the subject, and illustrate the range of applications: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dataverse#The_Dataverse_Project_Background

first-order resource to be managed alongside the corresponding data files, and not just as internal information utilized by the platform for the purposes of its own data management.

C. Dataverse, CESSDA, and DDI Metadata

There is a culture of Dataverse implementation within the DDI community, resulting from the shared domain background of the organizations which originally produced the software. Dataverse has implemented a core set of the DDI-Codebook metadata fields at the dataset level, and expansion of this set to the variable level is currently under discussion.

It is important to note that while DDI Codebook is a common specification for some Dataverse users, the software itself is not dependent on any particular domain standard. It allows for the inclusion of any type of domain metadata which could be deposited as a file, and proactively supports generic metadata schemes (such as DDI Lite, DDI 2.5 Codebook, DataCite 3.1, and Dublin Core's DCMI Metadata Terms). Domain metadata schema implemented in Dataverse include Astronomy and Astrophysics Metadata (VOResource Schema) and Life Sciences Metadata (ISA-Tab Specification).¹² Because Dataverse development is driven by its user community, it reflects the requirements of that community—by intention, it can be used in any scientific domain.

For many years, the community of CESSDA data archives within Europe had based much of their technology implementation for data sharing on the Nesstar suite of tools, a technology distributed by the Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD) and based around DDI-Codebook. Now, however, that suite of tools will no longer be maintained, and a replacement is needed by many of the archives as they move forward. Dataverse is viewed by many as a possible successor to the Nesstar tools, in large part because it already provides a degree of support for the common metadata holdings.

Evidence of this possibility can be seen in the SSHOC project, started in January, 2019. The project partners CESSDA, DARIAH, CLARIN and ERIHS are working together to create a reliable and production-ready open-source data infrastructure that institutes can install and reuse for their own needs and requirements, based on the Dataverse software.

Given that this is the case, Dataverse provides us an excellent example of a technology platform which might be able to serve as a basis for the implementation of DDI-CDI within a relevant EOSC domain, but one which might also be immediately applicable in other domains as well.

Dataverse has an ability to extract metadata from deposited statistical data files, including the creation of DDI Codebook metadata. One interesting implementation was recently demonstrated by Metadata Technology North America, in which DDI-Codebook metadata was programmatically derived from proprietary statistical package files when they were deposited into a Dataverse repository and associated with the data inside it, with enhanced variable-level metadata. (This application relied on a metadata-mining functionality labelled "Rich Data Services" by the implementers, which is more generic in scope than just its use within Dataverse. Details can be found at <https://www.richdataservices.com/>.)

This implementation illustrates an important point: metadata can be programmatically mined from data under some circumstances and encoded in a standard format. In this example, we see that the metadata from a typical set of tools used in the SBE sciences is extracted and encoded in a specific domain standard, but the principle here is not necessarily domain-specific: other proprietary data

¹² See <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/user/appendix.html>

formats could be deposited, and subject to metadata extraction and expression according to other domain standards or generic ones.

It is possible to derive DDI-CDI metadata from DDI Codebook (this was a use case in the development of the DDI-CDI model, and the specification contains a mapping between the two.) Therefore, one metadata expressed in the form of DDI Codebook can be programmatically extended into an expression of that same metadata in DDI-CDI with little or no user input and associated with the deposited data.

The two standards do not have identical metadata payloads: much of what is contained in DDI Codebook is user-oriented documentation at the level of the “study” (e.g., data set) which is not captured by DDI-CDI, and the way in which more granular descriptions of variables is approached is very different (DDI Codebook has no inherent concept of metadata reuse or use-by-reference, which is central to how DDI-CDI approaches metadata to support data integration.) Using “smart” metadata-mining techniques, however, it is possible to mine a granular, “reusable” DDI-CDI description of the data from DDI Codebook with a minimum of additional information.

D. The EOSC Context

The idea here is straightforward: if common domain standards exist within a cluster (e.g., DDI Codebook within SHOCC) or if they can be derived programmatically using existing repository applications, they can potentially be used to produce DDI-CDI programmatically as well. The cost of producing this standard metadata description is low and becomes almost a by-product of using the repository software (in this case, Dataverse).

The benefits are those which we saw above in the UKDA example: if data from a Dataverse repository is wanted for integration with other data in another domain (or within that domain by an institution with dissimilar types of data), the metadata needed for fine-grained integration and reuse would be available as needed.

The diagram below illustrates this idea:

Here, we see that a deposited file could, with minimal effort, result in a data set which is not just reusable, but which could be taken and integrated with other, dissimilar data coming from another source. In each case, the data which is input to the “integration process” is described using the DDI-CDI model, so that enough metadata exists to perform at least the structural integration programmatically. While some aspects of domain semantics would need to be solved, the structural description provides a solid basis on which to understand and implement needed semantic crosswalks.

Because a low degree of effort is required on the part of the depositor and repository manager, this approach to generating DDI-CDI metadata will help to reduce the amount of expensive “data wrangling” on the part of the end user but does not translate into additional manual effort on the part of the data providers. Such an approach indicates how issues of scale can be addressed with machine-actionable approaches.

The metadata mining which takes place in this scenario is non-trivial. Common formats and domain standards are used (in this case, common statistical package formats and the DDI Codebook specification, both of which are popular in the SBE sciences.) Each domain would need to equip its users with this type of metadata-mining capability, as appropriate to the technology and metadata culture within that domain. DDI-CDI provides the “lingua franca” which facilitates a negotiation across domain boundaries to support automated integration to the greatest possible extent.

This example is important for EOSC specifically because it shows that a popular platform which is in use already presents us with the possibility to begin to make the needed granular metadata widely available. FAIR data sharing, within and among domains, requires first that the sources of data are *shareable*, and the example of DDI-CDI operating in Dataverse shows us one way that this might practically be possible.

VI. European Social Survey Multilevel Application: Efficiency Improvements for Survey Data Integrated with National and Regional Data from Other Domains

A. Background

The European Social Survey (ESS) is an important, long-running survey covering 32 countries in the most recent round 2020. While there is a consistent methodology across countries, it is understood that each participating country will need to collect the “same” data in a fashion which is suitable for local conditions. This involves not only translation of the questionnaires used into appropriate languages, but also adjustments to meet the realities across a wide range of national environments. The task of data integration at such a scale is non-trivial.

As ESS data processor and archive, the Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD), provides a “multi-level” view of the integrated data¹³. The standard geographic scheme used for the survey (and indeed, within Europe generally) is the Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS), developed and maintained by the European Union. NUTS provides a three-level hierarchical breakdown within each country: the “regional” level (NUTS 1), the “state” or “province” level (NUTS 2), and the “district” level (NUTS 3). There is a further breakdown into local administrative units (LAUs). Because of the variety of size and administrative organization within the various countries in Europe, some countries will use all of these levels, while others employ only some of them: Germany

¹³ European Social Survey Multilevel - <https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/data/multilevel/>

has *Bundesland* (NUTS 1), *Regierungsbezirk* (NUTS 2), *Kreis* (NUTS 3), and *Gemeinden* (LAU), while Luxembourg has only *communes/Gemeinden/Gemengen* (LAU).

The “multi-level” provision of the ESS data at NSD reflects this geographic organization of the data, providing data at each of these levels and for individuals, depending on what is found in the data coming from each participating country. Additionally, it includes what is termed “contextual” data: reference data coming from other sources.

This website contains survey data from the European Social Survey and contextual data from Eurostat, OECD, UN, UNESCO, World Bank, Freedom House, WHO, Transparency International, IMF, Bertelsmann Stiftung, CIRI Human Rights Project, Democracy Barometer, The Comparative Political Data Sets and Database of Political Institutions.

The inclusion of contextual data enriches the ESS data but is accompanied by considerable additional effort: a large number of data sources must be included and integrated in a fashion which takes into account the nature and formats of the different data sets. The ESS data are collected on a two-year cycle. The contextual data are added one year after their release. The ESS data themselves are revised at frequent intervals, the contextual data less frequently.

The ESS itself is documented using DDI Codebook—the site operated by NSD is driven by the Nesstar technology mentioned in the preceding section. Contextual data may be described using other standards, depending on its source (for example, Eurostat uses the Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange standard [SDMX] with data being supplied in the multi-dimensional format supported by that standard.)

When considering implementing DDI-CDI, NSD would examine how efficiencies could be introduced in the process of large-scale data integration for the ESS. This could take several forms:

- Lower the cost of data integration
- Allow for more frequent updates of contextual data
- More easily process data revisions and changes to improve efficiency in the maintenance of the data

B. The ESS Multi-Level Application

The ESS data is available in a variety of forms and supports the selection of individual variables for combination into a customized data set by the user. The application can be seen here:

Dataset: ESS8-2016, ed. 2.1 - Multilevel Data

Climate change ca...activity, or both: Categories | [COUNTRY] GDP at ...e EU average 2017: Categories | Type: Column percentage

[COUNTRY] GDP at current market prices - Euro per inhabitant in percentage of the EU average 2017	40	42	50	60	63	69	83	95	114	118	129	132	135
Climate change caused by natural processes, human activity, or both													
Entirely by natural processes	3.2	0.8	3.3	1.2	1.7	1.9	1.1	1.4	2.1	2.2	1.1	1.0	1.3
Mainly by natural processes	7.3	6.4	13.8	10.0	4.4	4.8	3.4	4.8	4.0	7.1	4.6	4.3	4.7
About equally by natural processes and human activity	57.4	45.8	47.8	51.9	44.3	54.1	35.8	36.8	46.8	54.2	39.6	41.4	42.2
Mainly by human activity	28.6	36.3	29.6	28.8	41.0	32.7	46.8	45.2	39.6	32.2	46.1	48.1	45.1
Entirely by human activity	3.2	10.2	4.7	6.6	8.6	6.4	12.5	11.5	7.3	3.9	8.2	5.0	6.7
I don't think climate change is happening	0.5	0.5	0.7	1.5	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.1
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
N=	1,583	1,542	1,895	4,116	1,238	1,283	1,853	2,524	2,024	1,909	1,754	2,798	1,907

Functionality also exists for downloading data and its use in other analysis environments, but the online tabulation provides an excellent way for researchers to learn about the available data, and to explore it to determine what they wish to download for inclusion in their own research.

C. Efficiency Gains in Data Integration across Formats

The task of data integration for the ESS Multi-Level Application requires dealing with the integration of ESS data coming from different national sources, at different NUTS levels, as well as the considerable task of combining the contextual data, available in different forms, and documented according to different metadata models.

The ESS data itself is in “wide” form: that is, for any given data, each individual record is a row in a table, with each variable contained in a column. The data sets are collected at specific points in time. (This looks like the questionnaire data example described for the UKDA example, above.)

Contextual data comes in a variety of forms. To use the Eurostat example, the GDP data would be provided as multi-dimensional data cubes. In this case, each measurement is a derived value identified by a compound key made up of codes indicating the time period, geography, and a large number of other elements (the dimensions in the cube). This standard model—SDMX—is used by many but not all of the sources providing contextual data (IMF, OECD, and many UN organizations also use SDMX where they have suitable data.)

Currently, bridging these disparate data structures is a manual task, requiring the analysis and mapping of each different data source. DDI-CDI could, in this instance, act as a “lingua franca” for describing all of the data sources in a common way, enabling automated processing of the sources each according to its form.

As well as providing a model for both the “wide” (that is, rectangular) data formats described by DDI Codebook and used in the ESS data, DDI-CDI also provides a multi-dimensional model which is aligned with SDMX, and the Eurostat data. The publication version of the DDI-CDI specification will include mappings to both DDI Codebook and SDMX.

A degree of efficiency is gained by being able to automate the integration of data in different formats and described in different models. This capability actually becomes more significant in the event that any changes occur in the contextual data. Because these are external to the ESS, they cannot be controlled – each source will update their own data on their own terms.

If the cost of integrating contextual data can be lowered, by automating the integration on the basis of a common description in DDI-CDI, then two important effects will occur: first, the frequency of updating could be increased, to align with updates to the ESS data. This would lead to the second:

the reflection of changes in structure or content of those data sets could be reflected in a more timely fashion, potentially even when the ESS data for which they provide context has not changed.

In order to make this happen, each of the source data formats and metadata models would need to be mapped to DDI-CDI. In those cases where there is an existing domain model which is standard (as for DDI Codebook and SDMX) this already exists and would only need to be operationalized in processing tools. Other sources will need to be analyzed and mapped, either at the level of each data source, or at the level of whatever standards are used for that data. Once mapped and operationalized, any given update to ESS data or contextual data could programmatically be described in a DDI-CDI form, making such a description available for use as a “lingua franca” in further processing (this is similar to what we see with DDI Codebook in the Dataverse example).

In many ways, this application of DDI-CDI parallels what was seen above in the UKDA example, where an ability to compute across disparate structures can reduce the effort needed to perform data integration. Because the ESS and many of its contextual data sources use recognized international standard classifications (such as NUTS), in many cases the semantic mappings also already exist. These provide a strong basis for automation of the integration processing.

D. Datum-Level Maintenance

Another potential source of increased efficiency is perhaps less obvious. Given the scale of the ESS, it can easily be understood that revision to the data of the ESS itself will happen at frequent intervals, and the contextual data will also be subject to revision as part of its normal maintenance.

Currently, such changes are handled using an “edition” for any given portion of the ESS data. In the Multi-Level Application we can see this number in the left-hand navigation panel, associated with each year.

In order to update a single revised value in the ESS, an entire year’s worth of data must be re-processed. Understandably, these changes are not made individually, but are grouped into “editions” and made periodically, when enough revisions exist to justify the effort. Each time a new edition is created, all of the results of that process must be subject to quality control and various checks, whether any specific data point was revised or not.

DDI-CDI provides the ability to identify individual datums (that is, cells) within different data formats, once they have been described according to the DDI-CDI model. Further, the description of data processing is possible within DDI-CDI, so that data cells can be tracked across their different permutations as they are integrated into their final form. (The way in which such a process description can be programmatically captured is illustrated in the subsequent example for the ALPHA Network, see below.)

Given that each datum can be identified in reference to each form it takes during the process of integration, the potential exists for tools which would allow for more granular revision of data. If a cell in one of the input data sets is updated, the exact consequences of that revision could be computed, based on the metadata describing both its location within each relevant data set during integration processing, and on the description of the specific processes to which it was subject.

Again, this would result in more timely revision to the ESS Multi-Level data as inputs were revised, and would lessen the cost of wholesale “edition”-level processing and quality assurance, in order to accommodate a relatively small number of changes.

E. Conclusions

The ESS Multi-Level Application example is one which shows how DDI-CDI could be derived from existing metadata standards and sources, and then leveraged to increase the efficiency of maintaining integrated data sets which are already available. In many ways, the technical capacity for such efficiency gains relies on features of DDI-CDI which are similar or identical to those which could be used in an “on-demand” data integration scenario as described in the UKDA example. It is important to understand that DDI-CDI could also be used to help producers of existing integrated data sets such as ESS perform their work more efficiently. The key aspect of DDI-CDI which would enable such gains is its ability to act as a lingua franca across the diverse structures and metadata models employed by different domains and institutions.

VII. The ALPHA Network and INSPIRE: Integration of Data from Clinical Systems and Questionnaires Highlight Differences in Domains which Require Context/Provenance Information

A. Background

Two related examples serve to further illustrate the need for more granular documentation and management of data in a cross-domain scenario, and also the possibilities for capturing provenance metadata in a machine-actionable way. These examples are not purely European: they involve European institutions but are focused on African data: the ALPHA Network and the INSPIRE project.

The ALPHA Network builds on earlier efforts around health research, in which population studies throughout the LMIC shared data collected by Health and Demographic Surveillance Systems (HDSS) through the INDEPTH network¹⁴. This network inspired the development of a more focused effort lead by the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM) looking at HIV data collected not from clinics, but from the field. This is significant, because in many of the southern and eastern African countries which contribute to the ALPHA Network, much of the population does not have access to clinics. Part of the ALPHA work involved integrating data from several different sites to produce event data for analysis, and the documentation of this integration served as a test-case for the development of DDI-CDI’s process model.

The INSPIRE Network came out of the work on ALPHA. It is an on-going project which is focused on the integration of the population data from the ALPHA Network with clinical data, again with a focus on Africa. An extension to this project in Kenya and Malawi is now looking at how the same platform can be used for integrated data on COVID-19 (the INSPIRE PEACH project).

In order to integrate population data with clinical data, the INSPIRE data model—often documented in DDI Codebook—is being mapped against the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model standard (OMOP CDM¹⁵). The OMOP CDM is a model which is in widespread use internationally and has a good deal of uptake within the European community, with new companies providing services in this area (i.e., The Hyve¹⁶) and a growing user community (i.e., The OHDSI European Symposium¹⁷).

¹⁴ INDEPTH network - <http://www.indepth-network.org/>

¹⁵ Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model standard (OMOP CDM - <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/the-common-data-model/>

¹⁶ The Hyve - <https://www.thehyve.nl/>

¹⁷ The OHDSI European Symposium - <https://www.ohdsi.org/events/ohdsi-europe-symposium/>

Unlike population data, which is typically managed and understood as being organized into “data sets”, clinical data is generally managed as a set of data sources (e.g., databases) which can be shared. The managed package for such data is the clinical cohort, which is a more fluid construct than the data set. Data is treated as being part of an ongoing flow, largely because it comes out of clinical systems, rather than from discrete data collection activities such as the administration of survey questionnaires.

Thus, the INSPIRE example shows us how bridging between domains requires not just the mapping of data points, but a crosswalk between different data management paradigms.

Together, these examples serve to further show the kinds of requirements for cross-domain data sharing which EOSC faces, and which DDI-CDI can help to meet.

B. The ALPHA Network and Process Documentation

The diagram below shows the basic flow of data through the ALPHA Network:

At each site, the data held in existing systems is mapped to a standard specification, and (typically) documented in DDI Codebook. These inputs are reported through a local server termed a “Center in a Box” and reported to the LSHTM systems, where these inputs are aggregated. An open-source ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) tool called Pentaho is then used to clean and process the data in a multi-step process. The end result of this processing is then made available to researchers through LSHTM.

Within the ALPHA Network systems, the data are in a standard format (the specification against which they are being reported) and are coming from a known source. The processes used to integrate the data are similarly known, as is the resulting integrated data set. All of this information exists at the point where the processing is performed: within the Pentaho system.

Pentaho has a proprietary format for encoding the processing within it, which can be mapped into a more standard form (in this case, a combination of DDI-CDI for the processing flow, and a standard called the Structured Data Transformation Language, or SDTL, for the processing commands themselves). This captured provenance information is then supplemented with a small set of

information collected from the data reporter. The end result is a rich set of machine-actionable and human-readable information which allows the path of any given variable throughout the processing flow to be easily understood, from the form in which it was reported to the form it takes in the final analysis data set.

Key to this approach is the low level of effort required to create the documentation: it is captured as an artefact of the process, with minimal user input and less chance of error when compared to manual documentation. This system is currently under development but has been prototyped (Kanjala, Chifundo. *Provenance of "after the fact" harmonised community-based demographic and HIV surveillance data from ALPHA cohorts*. Diss. London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, 2020.)

For EOSC, the importance of this example is that while provenance metadata may be prohibitively expensive for data producers to create manually, it can be efficiently captured from the systems used to do the processing.

C. The INSPIRE Network: Integrating Population and Clinical Observation Data

The INSPIRE Network¹⁸ provides an example of how the different research paradigms around data can be effectively bridged. INSPIRE is an ongoing project which combines population data (including the data involved in the ALPHA Network) and integrates it with clinical data, typically observational data but also including other types of measurements.

The OMOP CDM is a data model which is conceptually based on the structures of relational databases: it is, in essence, a way of exposing data as an interoperable “data warehouse”. Each observation is associated with concepts, which both describe what the observation is measuring and supply the meaning of the recorded value of the observation. This value can then be contextualized, again through association with other concepts. Each concept in this picture is taken from a formal (and often standardized) vocabulary.

To perform an analysis, the user defines a cohort by specifying inclusion and exclusion criteria, couched in terms of the relevant concepts/vocabularies. This cohort can be formally expressed as a SQL query. When applied to an OMOP data source, the cohort results in a set of observations, which, when accompanied by the concept definitions, can be used for analysis. The data themselves take the form of a query result set, familiar to users of relational databases and data warehousing more generally.

This model is not entirely dissimilar to those commonly found in the statistical packages used in population research (e.g., Stata, R, SPSS, SAS, etc.). What it lacks, however—and this is a critical impediment to interoperability—is the notion of a “data set”. While an OMOP query result can be processed as a data set in these packages, it cannot be managed, exchanged, or cited as such. This has profound implications for issues around access control and confidentiality, which rely on a known set of possible combinations within the available range of data, so that non-disclosure can be ensured (it is often combinations of variables, rather than individual ones, which prove to be disclosive in population data).

The culture around population data does not typically include the notion of a cohort, at least not in the way it is found in clinical research. Specifically, the analysis tools for population data do not give

¹⁸ INSPIRE Network - <https://aphrc.org/project/inspire-implementation-network-for-sharing-population-information-from-research-entities/>

the cohort the primacy that it has in models such as OMOP (cohorts exist in population research, but they are implemented in different ways.)

When we consider the requirements for data interchange between these different domains—which is the focus of a project such as INSPIRE—we can see that a mechanism must exist for performing the crosswalk between them. Consider the diagram below:

Here, we see two different ways of realizing an analysis data set. One involves the selection of observations as defined by the researcher using a cohort. The other involves the design and administration of a survey. Both can result in a “data set”: for the clinical paradigm, this is the time-bound selection according to a specific cohort definition; for the population researcher, it is the set of responses to a questionnaire from among a population. This “data set” is interchangeable, and can be stored, cited, anonymized, etc.

There are two salient points which emerge from this, however:

1. A mechanism must exist for performing this crosswalk, because the inherent data set on the population research side is a matter of user definition on the clinical side. Until expressed as a “data set”, the population researcher will not natively know how to identify, request, or work with the clinical data.
2. The management of clinical data is done on the clinical systems which produce that data. Each separate source is managed independently, and OMOP allows for the different sources to combine into a notional pool from which cohorts can be drawn. On the population side, the analysis data sets are directly managed, as they always exist in some form (first as raw data, and then as processed data suitable for analysis).

It is clear that such an integration process is possible, but it requires that an informed transformation between these paradigms be developed. Both approaches emphasize the use of

concepts, although they are perceived slightly differently by the two domains (mostly a difference in terminology, but also in the specific structural roles they play).

Unlike domain-specific standards, DDI-CDI is able to show how concepts function to describe data in each of the two forms: as a “pool” of data (a Key-Value construction in DDI-CDI terms) and typically as a “wide” data set. The same concepts can be described in each case, being applied across the two structures. This is the critical structural metadata which is required to perform a crosswalk between these two systems.

The other critical piece of this is managing the packaging of data into data sets which can be access controlled and cited. This is not a difficult problem, as the OMOP idea of a cohort can be a time-bound selection of data from a known set of sources. The result of such a selection can be saved off as a data set. If the DDI-CDI metadata regarding the use of concepts to describe that data is available, then it can be documented as a traditional data set as appropriate to the type of user or analysis.

It should be noted that placing survey data into OMOP is less problematic: the responses simply become additional observations within the OMOP pool. Even this, though, requires having an understanding of how different concepts are used in relation to the data.

It would be possible to describe the INPSIRE integration of clinical and observational data within the OMOP-based system and expose the processes and provenance of the data in greater detail., but that goes beyond the intended scope of this example. This level of additional detail is shown in the diagram below, provided by Jay Greenfield, the architect of the INSPIRE (and INSPIRE PEACH) systems. It shows the flows of information which are occurring, and how they might be used in an analysis environment which is working directly from the OMOP CDM:

The application of DDI-CDI in describing the processes and data involved in these flows could be described using DDI-CDI as is suggested in the arrow at the bottom. This would provide a very rich source of information for integration with and reuse of this data to anyone wanting to work with it in an external environment.

Thus, we can see that a DDI-CDI description could be used to describe data drawn from the INSPIRE OMOP database for the purposes of a crosswalk into a dataset-based paradigm or could provide an even greater level of detail. In working with this data, however, it can be seen that a granular way of identifying and describing data is important. DDI-CDI provides this needed level of granularity, across the different structures considered here.

These kinds of crosswalks are among the many technical issues which are being addressed by the INSPIRE project. Given the importance of such integration in the modern world—especially in light of the COVID-19 pandemic—it can be understood that while the data in INSPIRE is African, the structural example is of direct relevance to EOSC.

VIII. DDI-CDI and the FAIR Ecosystem

A. Background

The ideas put forward in the article “FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship”¹⁹ have gained huge traction within the scientific data community broadly. The FAIR principles present centrally important concepts with admirable economy and “an arresting and rhetorically useful acronym”.²⁰ Just as importantly the FAIR principles set out to address the issues of scale and complexity by insisting throughout on the need to enhance “the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data” and to support “both human-driven and machine-driven activities”. Since their publication in 2016, a great deal of work has gone into exploring how the FAIR Principles can be manifested in the systems which manage and disseminate data.

There is not yet a full and precise technical specification of what “FAIR” means in terms of system implementation: there are many different ideas about aspects of the problem, being discussed within domain fora, but also in cross-domain ones such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and CODATA. Organizations such as GO FAIR have formed around helping science realize the promise of the FAIR principles.

Emerging from this work is not a specification, or a set of specifications, but draft proposals and discussions leading toward a more-complete vision of what a FAIR implementation entails. DDI-CDI has a role to play within the technical frameworks which are being proposed.

This example attempts to summarize the thinking around the “FAIR ecosystem,” and describes some of the possibilities, based on the capabilities of the DDI-CDI standard, and on the intense metadata demands which a FAIR ecosystem implies.

B. The FAIR Ecosystem

The Turning FAIR into Reality report presents a vision of the FAIR ecosystem which has gained traction and has been widely reused. The “atomic entity for a FAIR ecosystem is a FAIR Digital Object”.²¹ A FAIR Digital Object (FDO) could be a dataset, an individual datum, an algorithm, computer code, or any number of other types of digital research outputs or resources. In order to be FAIR, the FDO needs to have information and protocols ‘attached’ to it so that it can be understood and used by humans and processed by machines. These resources include (but are not limited to) Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), protocols and machine-actionable statements concerning permissions and licensing, and sufficient other metadata to allow the FDO to be found, accessed, understood and processed. Significant parts of the metadata will relate to the practices of given research domains and will cover provenance (the way the data were created and processed) as well as the definitions of the phenomena that were observed and the means by which they were measured or described etc. Although efforts are underway, no formal, agreed and implementable FDO specification currently exists, but at a *minimum the FDO can be understood as an agreed protocol for determining and operationalising the package of information surrounding (and required for the use of) a given digital object.*²²

¹⁹ Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJJ, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*. 2016;3: 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

²⁰ Turning FAIR into Reality. (2018) <https://doi.org/10.2777/1524> p.18.

²¹ Turning FAIR into Reality. (2018) <https://doi.org/10.2777/1524> p.39.

²² Cf. the draft ‘FAIR Digital Object Framework Documentation’ <https://fairdigitalobjectframework.org/> which describes the FDOF as comprising ‘a predictable identifier resolution behaviour, a mechanism to retrieve the object’s metadata and an object typing system’.

In turn, the FAIR ecosystem is described as those services which are necessary for such FDOs to operate. These include the services that provide persistent identifiers, machine-referenceable metadata specifications, vocabularies and ontologies and those that steward and provide access to data resources (data repositories and data bases of various kinds).

Recent work in the GO FAIR community on FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) seeks to gather information from various domains and research communities about the practices and implementation decisions to enable FAIR. This includes, for example, the metadata standards and specifications used, the vocabularies and ontologies which are necessary for that community’s data to have common meaning and to be interoperable. In sum, a FIP becomes a given community’s summary of its participation in the FAIR ecosystem from its perspective. This provides a “landscape” view of the ecosystem when all of the various community inputs are considered. These developments—the idea of FIPs and the work towards formalising the FDO—allow us to present a view of the FAIR ecosystem from a user-oriented perspective and to discuss how the role that DDI-CDI can play in the operationalisation of the FDO in the FAIR ecosystem.

The diagram below shows the roles that FIPs may play in the operation of the FAIR ecosystem:

FAIR Data Points (FDPs) are services (repositories, catalogues etc.) providing access to FAIR data or metadata. In the diagram above, the various FDPs within each domain also publish FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs), formalised descriptions of the resources, standards, and practices within that domain. These profiles are registered in a notional “catalog of catalogs” (more likely a distributed system for querying and locating FIPs). This would be organized according to various agreed domain classification schemes.

A user can query this register and locate sufficient information to find and query a FAIR Data Point within a domain, leading ultimately to the identification of data wanted for reuse, in the form of a FAIR Digital Object (FDO). This object would include references to the metadata needed for understanding and use of the object. (Such metadata would also potentially exist as FDOs, and would further reference each other, but might or might not be domain-specific in the sense that data are.)

Throughout this diagram, we see the fundamental FAIR principles in operation: it assumes that persistent identifiers exist, and that the resources mentioned are findable and accessible, and exist in a form which can—given sufficient metadata—be processed and used.

The diagram below shows in more detail the range of data, metadata, and related resources which might exist in such a system, specifically attached to an FDO (here in the narrower meaning, with which we are concerned, of a FAIR *Data* Object):

The red arrow denotes a notional “entry point”: a user retrieves a FIP and is guided to the relevant FDP. Interactions with the FDP will likely involve the use of various standards for data discovery such as DCAT, Schema.org, etc., and these will differ across FDPs. However, the FIP ideally will tell the user how to perform any querying.

As noted above, the FDO can be understood as an agreed protocol for determining and operationalising the package of information surrounding (and required for the use of) a given digital object. Examples of the types of information or resources are shown linked to the FDO above. In this example, we see the FDO comprising the data itself; structural metadata talking about the conceptual, logical, and physical organization of the data; a description of additional process and provenance metadata (which is likely made in reference to other related data and metadata resources); semantic resources and classifications, and additional resources such as crosswalks between semantic and structural systems elsewhere described, services for performing specific functions, etc. This listing is illustrative—we do not suggest that it is a comprehensive or definitive typology and there is likely to be a multiplicity of models describing the range of information types—but it does allow us to indicate where DDI-CDI can play an essential role in the FDO protocol.

Together, these diagrams serve to illustrate the different parts of the FAIR ecosystem and provide a framework for further discussions. DDI-CDI potentially fits into several places within this ecosystem, and exploration of this topic raises several interesting issues regarding FAIR implementation.

C. FAIR Digital Objects, FIPs, and Metadata

Given the types of metadata addressed by the DDI-CDI model, it is clear that it can play a role in several parts of the FAIR ecosystem. In any given domain, different sets of standards will be used; however, it is important to bear in mind that DDI-CDI is a generic standard, and one that will be applicable across domains and specifically in cross-domain integration.

We anticipate that the reference to a DDI-CDI description of data will occur when an FDO for data (a “FAIR Data Object” in the second diagram) is retrieved for processing. Once the data itself is obtained (and possibly even before it is obtained, if the user’s purpose is to assess the data) the various metadata resources will be retrieved.

The discovery of FAIR Digital Objects (and thus data objects) would be facilitated by the information provided by domains using FIPs, which would direct users to the data objects and could also indicate which metadata models and standards are used within a domain. In this sense, the existence of DDI-CDI metadata for an object could be listed as a resource which is relevant for the domain but not limited to it, as could the DDI-CDI model and its implementation artefacts (e.g., XML Schema, implementation guides, etc.).

Additionally, DDI-CDI can be used as a source for some types of metadata which occur elsewhere in the ecosystem. One example of this would be variable-level descriptions of data provided for discovery using a different standard format such as Schema.org.

In relation to the FAIR DATA object (as in the diagram above), we can see that DDI-CDI could play a role as structural metadata, as a useful form of process/provenance metadata, and as a meta-metadata resource, insofar as it can be used to describe the transformation required to perform a crosswalk between vocabularies. (This is addressed more completely in the section below).

The vision of the FDO Framework as a machine-actionable protocol, guiding users to the available relevant resources is important. This function will impact the direction in which DDI-CDI development progresses: there is currently a discussion about the modularity of the standard, which has as its objective to facilitate the flexible use of parts of DDI-CDI. Such an approach would furthermore support the emergent view of the functions of FDOs. (This modular approach is explored to some extent in the discussion of DCAT, below.)

When we consider how DDI-CDI fits into this ecosystem, it becomes clear that there are certain practical requirements. First, all of the functions described above must exist in a standard form for the approach to work: there are many different pieces to the puzzle, and they must fit together to support effective data sharing at a large scale. FIPs, FDOs, and DDI-CDI fill in some of the pieces, but there is also a role for semantic components, domain-specific metadata (i.e., DDI Codebook, DDI Lifecycle, OMOP CDM, HL7/FHIR, and many others) and process/provenance models, and so on. Alignment across the sets of standards, models, and protocols which will support the FAIR ecosystem is imperative and will actively involve the groups that develop and maintain them.

A second consideration is more practical: although metadata are often encoded using XML, RDF, JSON, or other such syntaxes, the data itself is often expressed in a pure text format (typically CSV files or similar). The range of technology platforms and languages requires that any solution of sufficient breadth to support the FAIR ecosystem described cannot rely on a single technology stack but must be adaptable to recognize both existing domain practice, and future developments both within domains and within the technology world more broadly.

DDI-CDI attempts to address this requirement by allowing the data it describes to be in whatever format is actually used (typically but not necessarily text-based), and by using UML class diagrams as a formalism for the model itself. This approach provides easy implementation across a wide array of existing technologies, and presumably could do so for emerging ones as well. It also provides a solid basis for aligning with, incorporating, and modeling to other relevant standards. This type of cross-standards activity has been highlighted by the DDI-CDI development team as of great importance.

D. A Typology of Metadata

One area where we do not yet have clarity is in the different types of metadata which are needed within the FAIR ecosystem. The diagram above suggests some basic types, and we can further understand that DDI-CDI can function as structural metadata, provenance/process metadata, and as a form of “meta-metadata,” used to inform other metadata processing. There is not, however, an easy way to identify how different standards and models fit together, because there is no widespread, detailed typology for the metadata needed.

This need becomes pronounced when we consider that many standards and models overlap to some degree, which can often only be understood by a detailed consideration of their coverage. One example of such overlap is between the work around Observable Properties taking place within ISO TC 211 and Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)²³, and the way in which DDI-CDI approaches the description of datums. These models are not directly equivalent, but they may provide a similar, granular functionality for describing data.

The I-ADOPT model²⁴ may potentially provide a way forward in this area. By modelling the patterns in how related data points qualify each other, it may allow for a better determination of whether two standard models for describing data are doing so in an equivalent fashion. This is still a very recent development, but further work may be needed in this area to allow for clarifications around a FAIR ecosystem. Without a common frame within which to evaluate the range of metadata provided by a given set of standards and models, it is difficult to identify whether any given domain is sufficiently “FAIR” to allow for effective data sharing.

As a practical consideration, it must be observed that the state of maturity as regards the dissemination of rich, standard metadata is low in many domains. This is a requirement for any FAIR data sharing and has been recognized as such. It is possible that having a typology of metadata as described here might assist in efforts to promote the publication of metadata more broadly, by making it easier to understand the different types of metadata and their purpose.

E. Semantics, Interoperability, and FAIR Metadata

DDI-CDI does not address issues around semantic interoperability. There is a strong culture around domain models and ontologies which describes the concepts and their application to data within a large and growing number of scientific domains. In addition to these, there is increasing attention being paid to multi-ontology approaches which can provide “bridges” between domains.

Most domain models do not attempt to model the structural aspects of data, however. Perhaps the key exception to this general trend is one of the best-known RDF vocabularies, Simple Knowledge

²³ OGC Abstract Specification, Geographic information — Observations and measurements, draft 2020 (jointly developed between the OGC and ISO TC 211) -

https://portal.ogc.org/files/?artifact_id=95653&version=2&usg=AOvVaw3v0mRsgmtclFEublbcHEQ

²⁴ Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG (I-ADOPT WG) - <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/interoperable-descriptions-observable-property-terminology-wg-i-adopt-wg>

Organization System (SKOS)²⁵, which describes concept systems. Because concept systems share a common structure, SKOS becomes useful across many different domains.

Formal concepts are also central to DDI-CDI, but it goes well beyond what SKOS provides in terms of how concepts are used in the description of data. Concepts play different roles in data sets, defining variables, the categories represented by codes, universes, etc. These uses of concepts are explicitly formalized in the DDI-CDI model.

Such formalized concepts can serve as a point of contact between the structural and process metadata which DDI-CDI describes, and the domain models which are the focus of many other ontologies and vocabularies. Because SKOS concepts and those in DDI-CDI can be equated, DDI-CDI can give us a more refined picture of how domain terminology and thinking is encoded in the structures of data sets. This allows us not only to answer the question “Are these terms the same?” but also the question “Is it important to understand their equivalence?”

Not every concept used in a data set needs to be mapped to every concept in a different data set for their integration: the meanings of data values must be mapped against the meanings of equivalent data values. Such concepts can actually be understood as the combination of concepts bearing on a single data point.

For example, the researcher may have a data set which has a variable defined as “Citizenship,” which might hold values of “European” and “Non-European”. A similar construct in a different data set might have a variable “European Citizenship” with values of “True” and “False” while a third variable in another data set might have a Variable “Nationality” with a country code. In each example, we can find a concept of European citizenship, but in each case it will manifest in a different fashion, and the formalization of the concepts will be arranged differently. In order to map the values between these data sets, we need not just a formal definition of their concepts, but also an understanding of how these concepts are used in a structural sense.

DDI-CDI gives us the structural understanding to determine which concepts must be mapped in order for the data to be made interoperable. While today this is almost always a manual process, with an understanding of how concepts relate, and of the roles they play structurally, we can envision solutions which are increasingly automated.

To support the use of external vocabularies, domain models, classifications, and concept systems, DDI-CDI provides both a model of such systems, and the ability to make references to external classification systems. In discussions with the Digital Representation of Units of Measure (DRUM)²⁶ group during the public review period for DDI-CDI, some of the requirements in this area were identified. The approach subsequently taken within the DDI-CDI development was a more generic one.

The ability to reference and use external classifications, vocabularies, and ontologies is seen as a critical functionality for DDI-CDI, in order to better support the mapping of semantics using other tools. This is a stated goal of the DDI-CDI development team itself.

For EOSC, DDI-CDI should function as a coordinated tool to help in the realization of a complete picture around data interoperability and sharing. Thus, it can be understood that while it covers

²⁵ SKOS - <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/>

²⁶ Digital Representation of Units of Measure (DRUM) - <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/drums/>

certain parts of the FAIR ecosystem, it must work in concert with standards addressing other needs, notably by adding structural awareness to systems focused on semantic mapping.

F. Issues and Questions for Further Study

When we try to assemble a picture of how the envisioned FAIR ecosystem could work in practical terms, there are many questions remaining. Some of these have been mentioned in the preceding text, but we will summarize them here, including some that came up in discussions but have not been addressed above:

1. ***Are all of the different user perspectives accounted for?*** Many discussions of the FAIR ecosystem see individual researchers as the primary users, but this may not prove to be the case. Research infrastructure is handled by dedicated staffs in many larger research institutions and government agencies, insulating the researchers themselves from any direct exposure to the technology providing their data. Further, providers of data often solve the more difficult challenges specifically so that their end users—researchers—do not have to. It remains unclear how EOSC, and its implementation of a FAIR data-sharing infrastructure, will answer this question.
2. ***How do data-provision services fit into this picture?*** In some domains, the sheer volume of data has led to a culture of data use where the data is not managed in individual, atomic “data sets” but is instead the result of the application of a query, provided through a standard services interface (i.e., geographic systems). FAIR does not fully address this type of data requirement, covering it in general terms only. How will this reality impact a FAIR architecture which seems to concern itself primarily with static data holdings?
3. ***How can adoption be sufficiently promoted?*** Barriers to entry into a FAIR ecosystem can be high, characterized by a demand for expertise in technology solutions which are unrelated to the focus of research (i.e., RDF). There are approaches to making participation in a data-sharing infrastructure easier and to promote adoption, but these often involve trade-offs in terms of the functions supported by the overall system. These issues have not yet been fully addressed.
4. ***Can automation be used to solve problems of complexity and scale?*** With tremendous computational capacity and sophisticated AI-based approaches, we have the basic tools we need to leverage automation in solving some of the challenges we face. This will, however, require a high degree of standardization and coordination which does not currently exist. In a world of ubiquitously sharable data, can we design and deploy an infrastructure that will meet not only the current demand, but the larger one which we will enable?

DDI-CDI can be part of an answer to many of these questions, and all of these have come up in the exploration of how it fits into a FAIR ecosystem. These questions remain open, however, and suggest directions for future work.

IX. DDI-CDI and EOSC: The EOSC Interoperability Framework and the FAIRsFAIR Proposal on Integration of Metadata Catalogues

A. Background

It is clear that EOSC and the EU community more broadly understand many of the issues being discussed in the examples above. In order to understand the best approach to deploying DDI-CDI

within this framework, it is useful to consider some of the thinking which is current within this community. There is an existing awareness of DDI-CDI as a potential tool for addressing some of the perceived challenges, but it is also clear that the picture is an emerging one, and that further clarity is needed.

Perhaps the single easiest way to understand current thinking around these issues is to consider the following diagram of the EOSC Interoperability Framework²⁷:

Figure 10. EOSC-IF Semantic view - Objects.

It should be noted that the term “semantic” in this document encompasses not only the definitional sense of the word, but also covers what has been referred to in earlier examples as “structural metadata” (it is used in this document to distinguish it from other aspects of interoperability: technical, organizational, and legal).

We can see here an alignment with the previous diagrams showing the FAIR ecosystem: the “Semantic Business Objects” associated with the FAIR Digital Object in this diagram can be understood as representing a typology of the types of metadata addressed here. Further, the green boxes to the right of the diagram labelled “Data Syntax”, “Open Format”, and “Identifier Scheme” are also types of metadata which could be seen as part of the structural metadata, although these have a slightly different application within the Interoperability Framework.

Importantly, there is a notion of a “Semantic Interoperability Specification”, highlighting the need for standards around implementation. Thus, it can be seen that the ideas around data interoperability are similar to the ones which we see driving the development and application of DDI-CDI.

In order to better understand the extent to which these ideas are similar, we need to look further into the details. As with the FAIR ecosystem, there are many open issues and questions remaining to be answered, and it is at this more detailed level that the utility of DDI-CDI can be best understood.

²⁷ EOSC Interoperability Framework, p40 - <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-190308283>

B. Metadata Types and Functions

The Interoperability Framework provides a further diagram²⁸ giving examples of some of the types of metadata shown in the diagram above:

There are some points which deserve notice here. DDI is mentioned as an example of “Domain Metadata” which is true but is in fact a recognition not of DDI-CDI, but of the DDI Codebook and DDI Lifecycle standards. As described earlier in this document, DDI-CDI is not focused on the SBE domain, but is rather a cross-domain standard of a different kind than earlier DDI specifications.

This difference is clearly appreciated. DDI-CDI is shown here as a “semantic structure,” which shows an understanding of its function in terms of the “semantics” described in this document. This is classed as “Conceptual Metadata” in terms of the first diagram, which is correct but perhaps does not fully explain the relationship.

There is a category of metadata here which is associated with the “digital object” (the FDO) termed “Minimal Metadata,” and here we see some examples which indicate of what this consists: schemes such as DCAT and DataCite are intended for discovery of metadata at the data set level. (A further appendix in the Interoperability Framework spells this out in greater detail.)

Implicit in this diagram is an understanding that different types of metadata support different functions. The “minimal” metadata are sufficient to find resources, but do not necessarily support use or integration of data. Conceptual metadata are useful in establishing the frame within which more granular metadata become meaningful (“Domain Metadata”).

This view is generally in line with what DDI-CDI is designed to do: it highlights specific, granular metadata which is needed to make data meaningful across domain and institutional boundaries, primarily at the structural level and the level of atomic processing, but also as a platform for definitional (“semantic” in our sense, not that of the Interoperability Framework, which is broader) metadata, ontologies/vocabularies, and other domain-specific metadata to become meaningful.

²⁸ EOSC Interoperability Framework, p41 - <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-190308283>

The definition of “semantic interoperability” provided by the Interoperability Framework gives us an excellent sense of what is needed:

*Semantic Interoperability. It ensures that the precise format and meaning of exchanged data and information is preserved and understood throughout exchanges between parties, in other words ‘what is sent is what is understood’.*²⁹ (from annex to “European Interoperability Framework - Implementation Strategy” p 25-26)

That the metadata needed to support different functions is conceptually at different levels is also appreciated. What we further need to understand is that these levels are themselves connected, and there must be a mechanism for navigating from “minimal metadata” used for discovery to the more detailed and granular metadata needed to guarantee full interoperability.

DDI-CDI covers some aspects of the full range of information needed to support semantic interoperability, and it is worth looking at how it could specifically be integrated into the less-granular metadata schemes which are proposed in the Interoperability Framework document.

C. DDI-CDI and Minimal Metadata: The DCAT Case

The FAIRsFAIR “Proposal on Integration of Metadata Catalogues to Support Cross-Disciplinary FAIR Uptake”³⁰ recognizes that both DCAT and DDI-CDI play a role in the cross-domain integration of data. It should be noted that DCAT (specifically, DCAT-AP which is the profile most widely used in Europe) is seen as being discovery-level metadata (an example of a “minimum metadata” set) and that DDI-CDI is a more granular form of metadata.

The EOSC IF recommends that ‘A minimum metadata model should be proposed in the future to ease discovery over existing federated research data and metadata (based on the reuse of existing standards like DCAT-AP, DDI 4 Core, DataCite core schema, etc.).’ Additionally, in the FAIRsFAIR case, a pilot project³¹ has been identified to explore the connection between these standards.

To support the improved discoverability of (meta)data catalogues by aggregators such as B2FIND and to increase interdisciplinary reuse, a small-scale pilot will be carried out between late 2020 and mid-2021. The pilot will trial the use of DCAT/DCAT-AP and DDI-CDI for (meta)data catalogues within domain e-Infrastructures (ESFRI clusters projects described in 5.1) and repositories (to be analysed as M3.7 ‘Identification of candidates for testing proposal on integration of metadata catalogues’). It is also important to underline that DCAT and DDI-CDI were among those recommended standards in FAIRsFAIR D2.4: 2nd Report on FAIR requirements for persistence and interoperability.

Specifically, the main aspect of data description to be provided by DDI-CDI within a DCAT frame would be a reference to the variables within a data set. On-going discussions between these groups indicate that such a use of the DDI-CDI “variable cascade” (part of the conceptual data description) as a resource connected to a higher-level DCAT catalogue description would be a critical connection

²⁹ Interoperability definitions in EOSC Interoperability Framework, p41 - <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-190308283>, cited from European Interoperability Framework - Implementation Strategy, 2017-03-23, p25-26 - <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/our-work/opinions-information-reports/opinions/european-interoperability-framework-implementation-strategy-communication>

³⁰ D3.6 Proposal on integration of metadata catalogues to support cross-disciplinary FAIR uptake - <https://www.fairsfair.eu/news/integrating-metadata-catalogues-support-cross-disciplinary-fair-uptake>

³¹ D3.6 Proposal on integration of metadata catalogues to support cross-disciplinary FAIR uptake, p33-35 - <https://www.fairsfair.eu/news/integrating-metadata-catalogues-support-cross-disciplinary-fair-uptake>

between the discovery level metadata and the more granular metadata required for reuse, including the identification and performance of integration processing on specific variables.

The envisioned scenario would involve the discovery of an FDO, with its attendant minimal metadata (expressed in DCAT), providing a link to the DDI-CDI structural metadata enumerating the specific variables existing within the catalogued data set. Once that connection is made, the DDI-CDI metadata can then be further explored to understand the roles played by those variables within the data set, and how they are represented (which might itself involve a link to the vocabulary or ontology of which the variable values are encodings).

This example illustrates a general approach in terms of how DDI-CDI and other models and standards can work together and is worth examining in more detail. The diagram below shows the kind of connection between DCAT and DDI-CDI which could be established:

Here we see a data set described with a DCAT-AP instance, providing the “minimum metadata” for it, including the title, publisher, frequency, and other DCAT fields. If there were to be a section describing the more granular metadata—the variables—then that section would not use DCAT elements for its description but would instead use the DDI-CDI description. These references would be to what is termed an “instance variable” in the DDI-CDI model. This would effectively expose two other “references” to any application reading the DCAT instance, which become important for scenarios where data is being integrated: the “represented variable” and the “conceptual variable”. Note that in the DCAT-AP instance itself, the actual reference is made only to the “instance variable”; the other references are implicit.

In DDI-CDI, the “instance variable” represents the variable as it exists in the data set: a value, represented by a code, number, string (etc.) and holding an associated value (from a vocabulary) in order to measure a concept. The specific data value in that variable is potentially reusable in a direct fashion: that is, it may be the same value with same definition and representation in another data set. This is, however, not always (or even often) the case. Instance variables are not reusable.

In the DDI-CDI model, the “represented variable” describes how the definition of the variable and its representation function (what vocabulary is used, and how it is coded, etc.). The represented variable is reusable: I can take the same definition and representation and use them in another data set for similar data. If I want to make two data sets comparable by design, I would have them share represented variables for the concepts I would use as the basis of an integration (same geographical measurement, for example). The represented variable can be used to group longitudinal waves of data across time, for example.

It is often the case, however, that two similar data sets measure the same (or equivalent) concepts—they have the same basic definition—but do it in a way which uses different representations or vocabularies. In this case, it is important to know the extent of the similarity, so that it can be determined that a crosswalk between the vocabularies is needed (etc.), even though the variables are measuring the same concept (that is, have the same basic definition).

By using the DDI-CDI model for its description of variables, DCAT-AP allows for a simple description of the variables in the data set to become available for reuse and data integration in additional ways, and helps to inform a system which is performing the data integration to know what is needed: a direct reuse, a mapping of the variable names, or a mapping of the variable names and the encoding of a shared vocabulary, or the mapping of names, encodings, and the vocabularies themselves. It is important to note that the DDI-CDI model makes these relationships explicit and supports the machine-actionability of the metadata.

In this scenario, we can see that while DCAT-AP is acting to provide the needed “minimum metadata,” an easy connection can be made to the more granular metadata using the DDI-CDI model as a framework. While DCAT is focused on cataloguing the data, it now acts as a gateway into the richer domain metadata needed to support data integration, comparison, and reuse.

Our investigation has indicated that different groups (the teams developing DCAT and DDI-CDI among them) are interested in supporting this pilot, and further exploring how this connection could be implemented in practical terms. Although this is only one example of how such a mechanism could operate, it is clearly an important one, and could influence the overall set of specifications suggested by the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

How the connection to specific vocabularies and domain metadata can be realized is a parallel case, and one which also requires further exploration. In the examples above, we mention the connection between DDI-CDI and DRUM around units of measure. Such examples might offer opportunities to further explore how this connection could be practically implemented. This work goes beyond what the FAIRsFAIR pilot is intended to cover, but it does follow the same line of thought as we navigate the needed metadata described in the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

Additional connections to domain metadata present additional, similar topics for exploration. In the examples above, we describe models such as the OMOP CDM for clinical data; a domain model which, if it can be mapped to a DDI-CDI frame, could then be integrated into an overall FAIR ecosystem. There are many such examples possible. In some cases, existing crosswalks could multiply the utility of such mappings (e.g., a mapping between DDI-CDI and OMOP CDM might further leverage a mapping between OMOP CDM and genomics data, which is currently a subject of investigation, providing the basis of a more general DDI-CDI/genomics data crosswalk).

Thus, it can be seen that DDI-CDI occupies a position within the overall Interoperability Framework which is very much in line with its intended use.

D. Large-Scale Interoperability in EOSC

Another area which is of concern within Europe is the establishment of a sufficient infrastructure for large scale data exchange. There are many aspects to this problem, not all of which are related to more technical standards such as DDI-CDI. One aspect, however, clearly is: issues of scale.

In “DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 20 June 2019 on Open Data and the Re-Use of Public Sector Information”³² we find the following (Article 27 p. 5):

The volume of research data generated is growing exponentially and has potential for re-use beyond the scientific community. In order to be able to address mounting societal challenges efficiently and in a holistic manner, it has become crucial and urgent to be able to access, blend and re-use data from different sources, as well as across sectors and disciplines.

This points out the issues of scale which Europe faces; exponential growth in the volume of data. From an infrastructure and interoperability perspective, the problem is exacerbated by the potential use of research data outside the “native” research community (e.g., in the policy sphere and elsewhere).

In the current climate, even the provision of “minimum metadata” for discovery purposes is insufficient to meet the envisioned problem. This lack is much greater when it comes to detailed, granular metadata such as that modeled by DDI-CDI. As we have seen in the examples above, the practical solution to meet the problems both of sheer volume of data, and of the creation of sufficient metadata to support its exchange and use, lies in automation. Notably, the automated capture of metadata from the systems which are used to produce and manage data (e.g., Dataverse, ALPHA Network) and the automation of data processes to the extent possible (e.g., the UKDA example).

Supporting such automation is one of the stated goals of the development of DDI-CDI, and again we see an alignment with European perceptions of this issue. In the publication “Turning FAIR into Reality” (section “3.2 Developing disciplinary interoperability frameworks for FAIR” on p 29) we find the following:

Rec. 4: Develop interoperability frameworks for FAIR sharing within disciplines and for interdisciplinary research.

Research communities need to be supported to develop interoperability frameworks that define their practices for data sharing, data formats, metadata standards, tools and infrastructure.

To support interdisciplinary research, these interoperability frameworks should be articulated in common ways and adopt global standards where relevant. Intelligent crosswalks, brokering mechanisms and semantic technologies should all be explored to break down silos.

And further:

Rec. 8: Facilitate automatic processing

³² DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1561563110433&uri=CELEX:32019L1024>

Automated processing should be supported and facilitated by FAIR components. This means that machines should be able to interact with each other through the system, as well as with other components of the system, at multiple levels and across disciplines.

Common sense suffices to tie these ideas together: a massive increase in the volume of data, combined with its broader application and the need for an increased quantity of metadata at different levels to support its use presents us with a new challenge. Existing approaches – the manual documentation of data, and metadata focused only on the discovery of data sets – will not be enough. Automation promises to allow us to meet these demands.

DDI-CDI gives us a model of one part of the overall solution: granular metadata described in a standard, cross-domain fashion. Without sufficient granularity, we will find ourselves locked into domain silos, and without standard specifications which support machine actionability, we cannot build an infrastructure which will meet demands of scale. DDI-CDI is conceived as a *lingua franca* between the domain specific specifications and high-level specifications such as DCAT and Datacite. It is categorically not intended to replace other specifications, whether domain or high-level.

X. Recommendations

A. Background

A number of issues are highlighted by the examples given above. These recommendations will focus on how EOSC can best address the issues which emerged from this work, specifically in terms of how DDI-CDI can help in a larger approach for the EOSC infrastructure overall. Note that the recommendations are not only given in terms of what EOSC should do with the DDI-CDI work product, but also in terms of interactions with the DDI Alliance to ensure that DDI-CDI is able to serve the intended role in the EOSC infrastructure. As a new specification with an anticipated early revision, it is both possible and likely that the DDI Alliance will be responsive to requirements coming from planned and ongoing EOSC implementation.

The main issues which emerge from our analysis are two:

- 1. *Issues of Scale:*** It is clear that the volume of research data is increasing, as is the demand for it. Further, the nature of the information needed to use that data—both in terms of completeness and machine-actionability, and in terms of providing sufficient context and background (“provenance”)—is likewise growing. This represents a combination of factors which demand that the EOSC infrastructure identifies practical solutions. The most likely key to success here would seem to be automation: machine-actionable metadata can multiply the ability of researchers to discover, access, and use data.
- 2. *Cross-Domain Data Reuse:*** In order to work across domain and institutional boundaries, a data-sharing infrastructure must provide a more complete description at all levels. The demand for data across domain boundaries is growing, and this comes with increasing challenges around the ability to easily integrate data from different sources. Some of the issues here are structural: data needs to be documented on a more granular level in order to reduce the effort to integrate data, and to support greater efficiency in this area. DDI-CDI is designed precisely to help address these issues by providing structural metadata and the datum level information captured through the variable cascade. Other issues are semantic. While DDI-CDI does not itself directly address the semantic issues, it can provide a firmer foundation for the application of semantic crosswalks and related technologies. It should be

noted that there is a requirement for more metadata broadly, both semantic and structural, and that it requires standard expressions to be useful.

B. Specific Recommendations

Given the summary of issues presented above, we recommend several areas of focus moving forward:

1. Enhance Support for Data Integration

Projects involving data integration which further explore and prototype the use of granular data descriptions at the variable and datum level using DDI-CDI should be supported. The ability to automate data integration to the greatest extent possible, and to allow researchers to perform more granular selections of data coming from different sources should be explored. Impacts on data disclosure should be analysed as a part of this work, as should potential efficiency gains on the part of data disseminators who perform an integration role in support of research. In the examples above, the UKDA integration of disparate types of data illustrates the value of such granularity, and the ESS multi-level example shows how such granular metadata might assist in making the provision and maintenance of integrated data products more efficient.

Possible further activities:

- Support projects exploring variable subsetting and datum level disclosure management, around these or similar data sets involving the UKDA (and potentially other partners), possibly involving data coming from the health sector through the PRUK or similar initiatives.
- Support the EOSC proposal involving NSD for the use of DDI-CDI in the ESS multi-level application, in particular for the efficiency improving management of datum level corrections and updates, and further explore whether there are generalizable approaches/tools which could be employed elsewhere.

2. Automate Metadata Capture

Platforms which can automate the capture of granular metadata with a minimum of manual effort should be identified as appropriate to different domains and their cultures of technology use. DDI-CDI is able to describe both data and provenance/process, and the machine capture of such metadata has been shown to be possible. In both the Dataverse example (for description of data) and the ALPHA Network example (for process/provenance metadata) we can see the ways in which this might function.

Possible further activities:

- Engage with the Dataverse open-source community through SSHOC and CESSDA, to further explore how such functionality might be implemented, and to provide a good domain example. This would include proactively engaging with the DDI Alliance regarding requirements for mapping between DDI Codebook and DDI-CDI products.
- Identify other domain technology environments where a similar approach might be feasible. Support this development both directly (through implementation projects) and in terms of encouraging publication of a mapping between DDI-CDI and relevant domain standards.

3. Develop Crosswalks to Domain Standards

DDI-CDI has been mapped to some domain standards, but the picture is far from complete. This work should be undertaken in collaboration with the DDI Alliance and any other standards bodies which are willing to participate. Agreed mappings and guidelines for use should be established which

support the role of DDI-CDI in the overall EOSC infrastructure. The nature of such domain relationships is illustrated in the example describing the INSPIRE network and its use of the OMOP CDM, and how this relates to a description of data in other more data-set-oriented domains.

Possible further activities:

- Engage with the INSPIRE Network to explore what type of integration would be possible between the clinical and population data involved in that project, and in data coming from other domains. Cross-cutting research around infectious disease, which might involve population and behavioural data, clinical data, genomics data, etc. could be candidate. Involving the OMOP community in Europe could be a part of such an effort.
- Undertake mappings to existing domain standards. Potential candidates include standards such as SDMX, GSIM from the world of official statistics, and the Data Cube vocabulary based on them, which is being used by the UN to publish SDG data. Other important specifications to be mapped could include CDISC for clinical trials, HL7/FHIR for healthcare, and Ecological Metadata Language (EML) in the environmental sciences.
- Identify European use cases for the further development of DDI-CDI to support those forms of data which it does not currently describe (e.g., large arrays of arrays as found in geo-physical data and some other domains). Engage with the DDI Alliance to ensure that these are supported.

4. Link DDI-CDI to other Metadata Standards within the EOSC Metadata Infrastructure

The EOSC IF presents a useful analysis of the types of metadata which are required for implementing a FAIR ecosystem for exchanging data within European research broadly. What is missing in this picture—both from the FAIR ecosystem perspective and (to a lesser degree) from the EOSC perspective—is a formalization of how different metadata models and standards interact. This includes further exploring mappings and coordinated use of standards such as DCAT-AP with DDI-CDI, and also includes establishing an agreed framework for the different types of metadata which have been identified, including not just “minimum metadata” but also vocabularies/ontologies, semantic mappings, etc. In order to move forward with implementation, more specificity and guidance on a technical level is needed, based on the identified capabilities of DDI-CDI and other standards.

Possible further activities:

- Extend the FAIRsFAIR pilot project around “Integrating Metadata Catalogues” to see how such alignments can be made practically implementable.
- Work collaboratively with DCAT and DDI-CDI to develop and publish a specific profile of coordinated use for the two standards in a European frame. Explore whether such alignments could be established with other generic standards for “minimum metadata” (Schema.org, DataCite, etc.)
- Pursue further specification of a FAIR ecosystem by supporting the alignment of DDI-CDI with FDOs, FIPs, and FDPs. Engage with the FDO work that is currently starting.

5. Establish Guidelines for Metadata Provision

Agreement on what constitutes a sufficient level of metadata within and across domains, and what constitutes best practice, should be made clear to the producers and disseminators of data. Expectations in this area are growing, and there is not a general agreement on many of these topics.

DDI-CDI could form an integral part of what is understood as shareable metadata for cross-domain use. Expectations and reference criteria should be established to facilitate the implementations of systems which can achieve the EOSC infrastructure vision in a practical way.

Possible further activities:

- Engage with efforts such as the CODATA Decadal Programme ‘Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges’³³ and relevant GO FAIR Implementation Networks and RDA groups to develop practical guidelines for the use of vocabularies, metadata descriptions (especially at a granular level), and technology approaches.
- Engage with Eurostat and other organizations in Europe which are responsible for establishing “official” standards and classifications/vocabularies within Europe which are used also in the scientific community.
- Ensure that the guidelines being promoted at an international level are coordinated with their European counterparts in EOSC, and that these are published and promoted effectively.

6. Support Technology-Neutral Solutions

DDI-CDI embraces one approach to working across technology platforms and tools. This is an important part of any workable solution, since the technology cultures across domains vary widely. The choice of a single technology is likely to become a barrier to implementation, and it is one which can be avoided by using model-based approaches which work across technology platforms.

Possible further activities:

- Explore the European requirement within domain clusters for syntax and technology platforms around metadata. Pass requirements in this area to the DDI Alliance to ensure support for them in the development of DDI-CDI.

7. Align with International Metadata Initiatives

DDI-CDI will be adopted in other, similar infrastructures. The effort which will go into the implementation of the standard elsewhere can potentially be leveraged within EOSC. Projects which will produce useful tools and approaches for EOSC, even taking place outside of Europe, should be supported.

Possible further activities:

- Investigate the mappings to OMOP CDM and related genomics and population data, taking place both in a European context but also in Africa through projects such as INSPIRE. Involvement in communities such as CODATA, RDA, and GO FAIR will help to ensure that such projects can be identified and supported in a strategic and beneficial fashion.

8. Align with Relevant Implementation Technologies and Platforms

Engage in technical activities around the models and their implementation to make sure that DDI-CDI is of use to technologists and implementors. To ensure the development of optimal syntax representations, technical alignments and integration with other specifications, models and technology approaches. This engagement would best be done through direct collaboration with the

³³ See <https://codata.org/initiatives/strategic-programme/decadal-programme/>

DDI Alliance as the coordinating body for further development around DDI-CDI, and the equivalent bodies for other specifications.

Possible further activities:

- Identify common technologies within the EOSC user community and undertake detailed work to chart requirements. Collaborate with the DDI Alliance and other standards bodies to develop a work programme for the necessary alignment and implementation. As one possible example, specific RDF implementations relying on standards like JSON-LD might be of interest in certain areas which could provide meaningful requirements for focused development.
- Explore the possibility of working with other data-sharing platforms existing outside the EOSC context. For example, consider efforts such as the NIH's Center for Cancer Data Harmonization (CCDH)³⁴ (to give one possible candidate – there are many.)

³⁴ CCDH - <https://datascience.cancer.gov/data-commons/center-cancer-data-harmonization-ccdhd>

Appendix – Acknowledgment of contributors

Many different individuals and organization assisted us in producing this report, and we are grateful for their support. A listing of our activities can be found in ‘The Role of DDI-CDI in EOSC: Report on Activities’ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4707290> with a record of the different meetings and events. We would especially like to thank the following individuals for generously giving us their time and attention, and for their participation in meetings and their feedback on the work:

Bodil Agasøster
Darren Bell
Danny Brooke
Luiz Olavo Bonino da Silva Santos
Oscar Corcho
Simon Cox
Mercè Crosas
Ron Dekker
Gustavo Durand
Alejandra Gonzalez Beltran
Jay Greenfield
Jon Johnson
Chifundo Kanjala
Hervé L'Hours
Barbara Magagna
Steven McEachern
Eva María Méndez Rodríguez
James Myers
Hilde Orten
Erik Schultes
Knut Kalgraff Skjåk
Carsten Thiel
Peter Winstanley